

**SiO-EMITTING CONDENSATIONS
THROUGHOUT THE ENVELOPE OF THE
YELLOW HYPERGIANT IRC+10420**

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IRC+10420 is a massive ($> 20M_{\odot}$), very luminous ($> 10^6 L_{\odot}$) star that is in the rare phase of evolution from the red supergiant to the luminous blue variable or Wolf-Rayet phase. Previous observations reveal that the circumstellar envelope is rich in molecular gas, and can be detected out to a radius of about $8'' = 6.0 \times 10^{17}$ cm. Observations in CO also reveal that the global mass-loss rate of IRC+10420 has changed dramatically over the last 6000 years, comprising two major episodes of mass loss lasting for about 1000 and 4000 years respectively separated by period of very low mass-loss rate lasting for about 1000 years. Surprising, previous observation in SiO($J = 2-1$) revealed a ring-like enhancement at a radius of about $1''$ (7.5×10^{16} cm) from the star, contrary to the expectation that SiO molecules should be frozen onto dust grains very close to the star (within $\sim 10^{16}$ cm). This ring-like enhancement has been attributed to a large-scale shock produced by interactions between faster and slower moving portions of the expanding envelope. In this thesis, we mapped the circumstellar envelope in SiO($J = 1-0$) to better constrain the physical conditions (gas density, temperature and SiO abundance) in the

SiO-emitting gas. We find a similar ring-like enhancement in SiO($J = 1-0$) but located further out at a radius of about $2''$ (1.5×10^{17} cm), and confirm that the SiO emission extends as far out as the CO envelope. The computed SiO($J = 2-1$)/SiO($J = 1-0$) line ratio significantly exceeds unity at radius out to about the location of the ring-like enhancement ($2''$), and drops to a value of about unity beyond this radius. From a one-dimensional non-local thermodynamic equilibrium model, we explore the physical conditions that can reproduce the observed brightness temperatures in both SiO($J = 1-0$) and SiO($J = 2-1$) as well as their line ratio as a function of radius. The SiO-emitting gas is required to have a density that is much higher (from a factor of a few to about two orders of magnitude) than has been inferred for the CO-emitting gas at the same radii. The required surface filling factor of the SiO-emitting gas depends on their unknown gas-phase SiO abundance; for an abundance of $\sim 10^{-5}$, as inferred just above the photospheres of low-mass evolved stars, the surface filling factor of these condensations range from ~ 0.001 to ~ 0.1 . Thus, the SiO emission from the envelope of IRC+10420 most likely originates from dense condensations that are immersed in more diffuse gas that produces the bulk of the observed CO emission. We reason that the SiO-emitting condensations correspond to the dust clumps detected in reflected light with the Hubble Space Telescope. These dust clumps are distributed from near the star out to a radius of $2''$, spanning the same extent as the peaks of SiO- (and CO-) emitting envelope. We show that these dust clumps are expanding in every direction away from the stars at a velocity that is significantly higher than the CO-emitting gas, and anticipate that shocks thus generated heats up the dust clumps to release SiO into the gas phase.

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November 2013

Declarations

I declare that this thesis represents my own work, except where due acknowledgement is made, and that it has not been previously included in a thesis, dissertation or report submitted to this University or to any other institution for a degree, diploma or other qualifications.

WONG Ka Tat

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Chapter 1

Nature of IRC+10420

IRC+10420 (V1302 Aquilae, IRAS 19244+1115) is one of the very few stars in the sky whose spectral type appears to have changed in less than a human lifetime. The spectral type of IRC+10420 has changed from F8 in the 1970s (Humphreys et al., 1973) to A2 in the 1990s (Oudmaijer, 1998; Klochkova et al., 2002), corresponding to an increase in “effective temperature” from ~ 6000 K to ~ 9200 K in only three decades. Yet, over this period, the star has maintained an essentially constant brightness (Oudmaijer et al., 1996; Humphreys et al., 2002). Humphreys et al. (2002) argue that the change in spectral type does not correspond to an actual change in the effective temperature of the star over such a short time interval. Rather, they attribute the change in the apparent effective temperature to a decrease in opacity of a massive wind from the star as the wind expands (and the mass-loss rate of the star since decreased), thus allowing us to see a deeper layer of the stellar wind at a higher temperature.

IRC+10420 is surrounded by copious dust and molecular gas ejected by the star over the last ~ 4000 years (assuming a constant expansion velocity of ~ 38 km s $^{-1}$), making it among the brightest infrared sources in the sky. Prodigious mass-loss in the recent past has been directly imaged in infrared

and optical (e.g. Humphreys et al., 1997; Tiffany et al., 2010), in which a huge ($\sim 6''$) and roughly spherical circumstellar dust envelope, with numerous complex small-scale structures (referred as knots, jets, etc.), was observed. The circumstellar envelope has also been imaged in molecular gas, thick molecular gas envelope traced in various transition lines (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009) provide direct evidence for the huge amount of circumstellar materials. The global geometry of the dust shell and molecular gas envelope resembles spherical symmetry, although localized clumpy regions and slight departure from spherical symmetry are observed.

Although there is little doubt that IRC+10420 is an evolved star, a greater understanding of the nature of IRC+10420 is very much tied to a correct inference of the distance to this star. Historical estimates give values ranging from around 3.4 kpc to 6.8 kpc. If the correct distance to the star is at the lower end in the current range of distance estimates, then IRC+10420 would be a low-mass AGB or post-AGB star. If the correct distance is at the higher end, then it would be a massive, luminous supergiant or post-red supergiant. As we will explain in Section 1.2, indirect evidence such as the very strong blended oxygen O I triplet in the spectrum of IRC+10420 (e.g. Humphreys et al., 1973) and high outflow velocities from multi-wavelength observations (e.g. Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009) indicate that it is more likely to be a supergiant. If so, then IRC+10420 has a luminosity class of around I, and is located near the top of the Hertzsprung-Russell (H-R) diagram for stars of its spectral type. Figure 1.1, shows the plot of the H-R diagram indicating the position of IRC+10420 just beneath the empirical luminosity limit for stars of the respective spectral types (also known as the Humphreys-Davidson limit). Based on its assumed distance of 5 kpc, IRC+10420 is widely classified as a yellow hypergiant – a rare class of very luminous, highly evolved star in the general transition from a red supergiant to a luminous blue variable, Wolf-Rayet star or even supernova. Stars at this evolutionary stage are believed to exhibit “bouncing” motion on the H-R diagram by moving bluewards and redwards in a short

Figure 1.1: The position of IRC+10420 in the H-R diagram if the distance is assumed to be 5 kpc from Earth. The thick horizontal bar of IRC+10420 represents the range of its apparent spectral type inferred historically. The long, kinked line above the star represents the empirical upper limit, also known as the Humphreys-Davidson Limit, of stellar luminosity for the corresponding spectral type. (Taken from Figure 14 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

timescale (of decades), indicating rapid changes in the apparent spectral type (or the apparent “effective temperature”).

In the next few sections, we will describe relevant observations and critically examine the arguments for the spectral type, distance (and hence luminosity) and evolutionary status of IRC+10420 as a yellow hypergiant.

1.1 Spectral type of IRC+10420

Accurate information on the spectral type is essential to precisely identify IRC+10420 on the H-R diagram and hence possibly investigate its evolutionary status. However, as we now understand, the effective temperature of IRC+10420’s photosphere, which is the primary indicator of the spectral

type, is extremely difficult to estimate accurately because of the optically thick wind preventing direct measurement of photospheric fluxes (Jones et al., 1993; Humphreys et al., 2002). There is no direct evidence “proving” that the stellar photosphere is obscured by the “pseudo-photosphere” which is optically thick at continuum. The strongest observational (indirect) evidence is from the high-resolution (both spectral and spatial) spectro-interferometric observations of Br γ (a hydrogen recombination line requiring ionization of hydrogen atoms) and Na I (*neutral* sodium) lines (Driebe et al., 2009; Oudmaijer & de Wit, 2013), in which the size of spatially resolved line-emitting region of Na I is, very unusually, closer to the star than Br γ . Oudmaijer & de Wit (2013) suggested that this indicates the emission region for the neutral sodium lines is shielded from ionizing photons from the star by the optically thick wind, while (collisionally-)excited hydrogen atoms can still be ionized by less energetic photons.

Furthermore, calculations of quantities related to the wind opacity have been done to infer an optically thick wind around IRC+10420. Humphreys et al. (2002), using the method of “wind density parameter” ($Q(T_0)$) as defined by Davidson (1987) and adopting typical values of the mass-loss rate ($\gtrsim 3 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$, inferred from molecular ^{12}CO emission) (Knapp & Morris, 1985), expansion velocity ($\sim 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, inferred by fitting a geometric model as described above) and stellar luminosity ($\sim 10^{5.70} L_{\odot}$) for IRC+10420, derived a large value for the “wind density parameter”, thus concluding the opaque nature of the wind. We also estimated the wind opacity assuming the wind is entirely radiatively-accelerated. As we show in Appendix B, the wind opacity τ is around 1 as derived from the conservation of momentum, $\dot{M}v_{\infty} \simeq \tau(L_*/c)$ (e.g. Kochanek, 2011). However, we believe the adopted value of mass-loss rate, $\dot{M} = 3 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ (e.g. Humphreys et al., 2002; Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007) is just the minimum value. Higher values of mass-loss rate have been suggested (e.g. Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009) and therefore the actual opacity of the wind should be higher than 1, at least for the localized

denser regions. This is consistent with the presence of a pseudo-photosphere (Kochanek, 2011). This conclusion is consistent with the unexpectedly rapid change of spectral class in only ~ 20 years from the 1970s to 1990s, which is not believed to be due to the real changes in stellar parameters and evolution stage. We will outline below the corresponding observational evidence for such a rapid change in the (apparent) spectral class. We need to stress that only the increase in the apparent “effective temperature”, instead of the accurate value, is meaningful in this context (to demonstrate a rapid change in spectral type which should not correspond to real stellar evolution).

IRC+10420 has been initially classified as a F- or even early G-type star, corresponding to an apparent “effective temperature” of around 6000 K. Humphreys et al. (1973) has classified it as an F8- or G0-type star from spectra taken in 1972 at the optical blue and near-infrared wavelengths. The detection of strong, blended oxygen O I triplet at 7774\AA by Humphreys et al. (1973) also supports this classification as the line is greatly enhanced for supergiants in the spectral type of A–F (Faraggiana et al., 1988). Fix (1981) compared the optical and near-infrared spectra of IRC+10420 observed in 1980 with a F8 Ib star, γ Cyg, and found that IRC+10420 has weaker absorption lines in calcium, silicon and iron. These show IRC+10420 also resembled a late-F star in 1980, but probably not exactly at F8 as Humphreys et al. (1973)’s earlier spectra (of lower spectral resolution) revealed. Thompson & Boroson (1977) has observed the spectral range around $2\mu\text{m}$ in June 1976 and showed the absence of absorption or emission of $\text{Br}\gamma$ line from the spectrum; Fix & Cobb (1987) were also unable to detect any $\text{Pf}\beta$ and $\text{Pf}\delta$ absorption or emission lines in June 1984. In Figures 1.2 and 1.3, we show the infrared spectrum of IRC+10420 as obtained by Thompson & Boroson (1977) in June 1976 and compare it with a series of F- and G-type supergiant spectra (as we now believe IRC+10420 is a supergiant rather than a giant) published by Rayner et al. (2009). From the relative strengths of the Brackett series absorption as indicated in the top panel of both figures, we can see that the spectrum of IRC+10420 resembles

more to those of later spectral types like the F8 or early G. Therefore, the very first spectral classification of around F8-type was likely to be correct and therefore generally accepted until new spectrometric and photometric evidence arose.

Evidence that IRC+10420 had evolved to an earlier spectral type came in mid-1980s. An earlier spectral type may be inferred from the presence of hydrogen emission lines because recombination occurs when more atomic hydrogen were ionized by increased photospheric temperature. Spectral ranges for hydrogen recombination lines were covered in both Humphreys et al. (1973)'s and Fix (1981)'s work, but none of them reported any hydrogen recombination lines and hence there was no evidence supporting a different spectral class than late F for IRC+10420 by 1980. The first report for the detection of hydrogen emission line comes from Irvine & Herbig (1986) in which $H\alpha$, Ca III triplet and [Ca III] forbidden lines were found in emission in December 1986. These results may be indicating increased photospheric temperature. However, no detailed analysis on the emission lines to infer the corresponding photospheric temperature was provided by Irvine & Herbig (1986). Oudmaijer et al. (1994) also detected, in August 1992, a series of hydrogen recombination lines in emission, including $H\alpha$, $Br\alpha$, $Br\gamma$ and $Pf\gamma$ which were previously not seen in emission or absorption. $Pf\beta$ line was also detected in emission in August 1993 (Oudmaijer, 1995), in contrast to the non-detection in June 1984 (Fix & Cobb, 1987). Oudmaijer et al. (1994) therefore pinpointed the onset of hydrogen line emissions within the time frame from June 1984 to December 1986 and associated it with a new mass outflow being ionized. An earlier spectral type for IRC+10420 was motivated by the results from two independent observational techniques. First, optical photometry has showed increases in the apparent "effective temperature". Oudmaijer et al. (1996) have taken optical photometry on IRC+10420 in 1992 and compared the results with Craine et al. (1976)'s as taken in 1974. They found a decrease in near-infrared J and K band fluxes within 20 years, while the flux for V band remained constant (Oudmaijer

Figure 1.2: The top panel shows the H -band spectrum of IRC+10420, corrected for telluric absorption, taken in June 1976 (Taken from Figure 2 of Thompson & Boroson, 1977); the bottom panel shows the H -band spectra of selected F-type supergiants, normalized to unity at $1.6\mu\text{m}$ and offset by constants (Taken from Figure 52 of Rayner et al., 2009).

Figure 1.3: The top panel shows the H -band spectrum of IRC+10420, corrected for telluric absorption, taken in June 1976 (Taken from Figure 2 of Thompson & Boroson, 1977); the bottom panel shows the H -band spectra of selected G-type supergiants, normalized to unity at $1.6\mu\text{m}$ and offset by constants (Taken from Figure 70 of Rayner et al., 2009).

et al., 1996). Through quantitative model fitting, they proposed two possibilities – a constant photospheric effective temperature and a decrease in stellar bolometric luminosity, together with a simultaneous decrease in circumstellar extinction only at the visual band, A_V , to compensate the change in V band flux without affecting the infrared bands; or, an increase in effective temperature by at least 1000 K and constant bolometric luminosity and extinctions. Clearly, the later explanation is simpler and more natural because it does not require a coincidence in the amount of decrease in visual extinction. Independent to Oudmaijer et al. (1996)’s work, Klochkova et al. (1997) determined an even higher effective temperature, 8500 K, based on the intensity of various Fe I lines obtained in 1992, 1995 and 1996. Second, spectra of IRC+10420 were compared with those from other stars of different spectral types, similarly to Humphreys et al. (1973). Oudmaijer (1998) obtained the spectrum of IRC+10420 taken in July 1994, as shown in Figure 1.4 (i.e. Figure 1 of their paper), and concluded that the spectral type should lie between A2 and F0, more probably earlier than A5 (Oudmaijer, 1998). Klochkova et al. (1997) also did a similar and independent comparison and found that IRC+10420’s spectra, taken in 1995–1996, most likely resembles those of A5 stars (see their Figure 2). As we compared previously in Figures 1.2 and 1.3 that Thompson & Boroson (1977)’s infrared spectrum (their Figure 2) of IRC+10420 resembles most those of F8 or early G-type supergiants, the change in the apparent spectral type of IRC+10420 is clear.

Even if the spectral type, or the apparent “effective temperature”, is not known to the best precision, we can safely conclude that the apparent “effective temperature” has increased dramatically because independent observations using different techniques all point consistently to this suggestion. However, it is extremely unlikely for a star to evolve from late F to at least mid-A such rapidly in just two decades. No existing stellar evolution model can account for this. Jones et al. (1993) were the first to suggest that removal of dust from the hot, inner circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 might lead to a reduction in circum-

Figure 1.4: Optical spectrum of IRC+10420, taken in July 1994, compared with those of A – late F-type supergiants (Taken from Figure 1 of Oudmaijer, 1998).

stellar dust extinction, and hence the exposure of the even hotter interior and brightening effect as observed from the outside of the “pseudo-photosphere”. Although this suggestion was proposed to explain the long-term (few decades) photometric variation from 1926 to \sim 1970 in B -band (Gottlieb & Liller, 1978) and from 1965 to 1992 in K -band (Jones et al., 1993), it is currently accepted as the most plausible explanation to explain the rapid, apparent change in spectral type of IRC+10420 (Humphreys et al., 2002). In other words, any attempt to infer the “effective temperature” would only provide information of the surface of the opaque winds (i.e. “pseudo-photosphere”) rather than the genuine stellar photosphere. The intrinsic spectral type of the star therefore cannot be inferred directly.

1.2 Distance to IRC+10420

A more precise identification of IRC+10420’s evolutionary status requires a precise measurement of its distance and hence its luminosity. Various observations have estimated the distance of IRC+10420 from us to range from 3.4 kpc (e.g. Mutel et al., 1979) to 6.8 kpc (e.g. Giguere et al., 1976; Jones et al., 1993). If the distance to IRC+10420 is among the smaller values, say about 3 kpc, then its stellar luminosity as inferred from the apparent magnitude would be about $8 \times 10^4 L_{\odot}$ (assuming the visual extinction A_V of 6.0), thus placing the star among other less massive evolved stars in the H-R diagram. In this case the star should be interpreted as a post-asymptotic giant branch (AGB) star or a proto-planetary nebula (PPN). Conversely, if the distance of IRC+10420 is 6 – 7 kpc, then the derived luminosity would be at least $10^5 L_{\odot}$ or even higher. This will place the star at the top of the H-R diagram for stars of its spectral type, among the most luminous stars of the same spectral type that define the empirical upper luminosity limit (sometimes known as the “Humphreys-Davidson limit”) for stars in the Milky Way and Magellanic

Clouds (Humphreys & Davidson, 1979, 1984). We will examine in more detail below the arguments for lower and higher values for the distance estimate respectively and explain why we adopt the typically assumed value of 5 kpc.

The lower distance estimate is based primarily on two arguments. First, Mutel et al. (1979) estimate a photometric distance to IRC+10420 of 3.9 kpc by adopting an apparent visual magnitude of $m_V = 11.84$, dust extinction of $A_V = 6.9$ (as deduced from reddening of visual spectral energy distribution, SED) (Craine et al., 1976), and assuming an absolute visual magnitude of $M_V = -8$ for IRC+10420, as is the mean value for F8 Ia stars (Blaauw, 1963). Apart from the uncertainty involved by taking the mean absolute magnitude, the visual magnitude from other F8 Ia stars may not be related to IRC+10420 at all. If as is now believed, the apparent “effective temperature” of IRC+10420 may just be the surface temperature of the opaque circumstellar envelope rather than that of the stellar photosphere. Thus luminosity calibration method adopted by Blaauw (1963) is unreliable for the case of IRC+10420. Second, Mutel et al. (1979) compared IRC+10420 with other OH/IR supergiants and argued that if the distance of the star is 6.8 kpc, then its vertical distance from the galactic plane would be at least twice as far as all the others, and the OH maser would be at least five times as luminous as the others. Therefore, Mutel et al. (1979) concluded that the distance of IRC+10420 from us should be reduced by roughly half to 3.4 kpc. The underlying actual spectral type of the star, as obscured by the opaque wind, should therefore be earlier than F type, making Mutel et al. (1979)’s comparison made with M-type supergiants incorrect.

By contrast, there are arguments to support a larger distance to IRC+10420. Jones et al. (1993) detect a very high $B - V$ colour excess ($E(B - V) \approx 2.2$) for IRC+10420, resulting in a large extinction $A_V = E(B - V) \times R_V = 6.8$, where $R_V = 3.1$ (e.g. Mathis, 1990). They argue the large reddening is caused primarily by interstellar rather than circumstellar extinction (Jones et al., 1993). Interstellar extinction A_V can be inferred from the amount

of interstellar polarization $p_{V,ISP}$ through the empirical relation, $p_{V,ISP}/A_V \leq 3 \text{ \% mag}^{-1}$, as given by Serkowski (1973). Jones et al. (1993)'s multi-band polarimetric data shows the interstellar polarization is nearly $p_{V,ISP} \sim 20\%$, obtained by fitting the multi-band polarimetric data to the empirical formula $p_{ISP}(\lambda)/p_{\max} = \exp[-1.15 \ln^2(\lambda_{\max}/\lambda)]$ (Serkowski, 1973). However, Jones et al. (1993) made an assumption that the position angle remained constant across wavelengths which was found to be incorrect. Despite that, a minimum value of $p_{V,ISP} = 12.5\%$ was obtained by Craine et al. (1976) using similar approach. Therefore, the interstellar extinction A_V is inferred to be at least 4 mag, and probably 6–7 mag (Craine et al., 1976; Jones et al., 1993). As the total extinction is just about 7 mag based on the colour excess of $E(B - V) \sim 2.2$ (Jones et al., 1993), the interstellar must be much larger than the circumstellar extinction. In order to reconcile the huge infrared excess in IRC+10420, which indicates significant circumstellar extinction in the infrared, Jones et al. (1993) required a tilted disk geometry for the circumstellar materials, leaving the extinction of at most 1 mag at V -band. However, the tilted (but not completely pole-on) disk geometry is not supported by most, if not all, later results. Different geometries for the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 have been proposed including bipolar outflow beaming nearly along the line-of-sight (Oudmaijer et al., 1994), roughly spherically symmetric envelope (Humphreys et al., 2002), multiple shells with departure from spherical symmetry (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009), pole-on viewing equatorial flows (Tiffany et al., 2010), etc. In particular, direct imaging of the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope in the radio wavelengths reveal a global spherically symmetric geometry (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009). As we know the total amount of molecular gas as inferred from radiative transfer modelling, we can explicitly calculate the amount of circumstellar dust extinction. As we show in Appendix A, the circumstellar extinction of molecular gas, as traced by ^{12}CO , is estimated to be about 3.5 mag. Even if there is local departure from spherical symmetry, there is no

strong reason to assume a nearly pole-on geometry. If the envelope is roughly spherically symmetric and smooth, the actual fraction of circumstellar extinction is likely to be higher than what Jones et al. (1993) expected and the lower limit of the distance may be even lower. One possible way to resolve the apparent contradiction between a small circumstellar extinction ($A_V < 1$ mag, based on polarization measurements) and a high dust content (from CO/IR measurements) is if the circumstellar envelope is very clumpy as we believe to be the case from ^{28}SiO observations, for which we will discuss in detail in this thesis. If the circumstellar envelope is very clumpy, the corresponding extinction may be small because the gas distribution is highly localized (i.e. small filling factor). In this situation, we can still observe a smooth envelope from interferometric maps because of the limitations in spatial resolution. On the other hand, it is also possible that significant amount of reddening is caused by circumstellar but not interstellar materials. In such case, the less interstellar contribution would lead to a smaller inferred distance of the star and hence its luminosity. Yet we will explain below that IRC+10420 is distinguished from AGB or post-AGB stars based on clues other than distance estimates.

The kinematic distance was derived to be 5.8 kpc (Jones et al., 1993). This estimate assumes that IRC+10420 is at the tangent point of its orbit around the Galactic Centre, moving radially away from the sun (i.e. the radial velocity aligns with our line of sight) and adopts a stellar velocity of 75 km s^{-1} . The stellar velocity of around 75 km s^{-1} , assumed to be the mid-point of the two peaks in 1612 MHz OH spectrum as observed by Giguere et al. (1976), is supported by at least two other independent observations. The maximum point of the H I line as observed by Jones et al. (1993), and the model fit of the line profiles in ^{12}CO transitions (Oudmaijer et al., 1996) both agrees very well with 75 km s^{-1} . However, the assumption that the star is located at the tangent point is not justified and this estimate only provides a possible upper distance limit.

As we have pointed out previously, the actual distance of IRC+10420 would affect the inferred stellar luminosity and hence our interpretation of its identity – whether it is a less massive AGB or post-AGB star, or a massive supergiant or post-red supergiant (post-RSG). We therefore consider indirect evidence which may provide hints to the nature of this evolved star. One example is through the relation between absolute visual magnitude (M_V) and the equivalent width of oxygen triplet at 7774\AA ($W_{7774\text{\AA}}(\text{O I})$). The equivalent width of blended oxygen O I triplet at 7774\AA is known to be a good indicator of stellar luminosity (e.g. Keenan & Hynek, 1950). If the equivalent width is larger, then the gas pressure must be lower because the triplet is produced by (neutral) oxygen atoms at upper metastable levels, which is subject to collisional de-excitation under high gas pressure. For such a diffuse atmosphere, high stellar luminosity is required to exert radiative pressure on the dust and gas, thus producing an extended, low-gravity ($\log g$) atmosphere (e.g. Faragiana et al., 1988; Arellano Ferro et al., 1991). Klochkova et al. (2002) has taken spectra of IRC+10420 from 1997 to 2000 and obtained a huge equivalent width of $W_{7774\text{\AA}}(\text{O I}) = 2.8\text{\AA}$. Using their self-derived calibration law between M_V and $W_{7774\text{\AA}}(\text{O I})$ (because available laws do not include calibration stars of such a large equivalent width), Klochkova et al. (2002) found that $M_V = -9.5 \pm 0.4$ for IRC+10420. If the extinction at visual band is around $A_V = 7.0$ (Humphreys et al., 2002), then the distance of IRC+10420 would be 5 kpc. We need to stress that, despite the lack of large- $W_{7774\text{\AA}}(\text{O I})$ calibrators, all existing calibration laws of M_V - $W_{7774\text{\AA}}(\text{O I})$ shows a very negative visual magnitude (and hence very high luminosity) under such a huge equivalent width (2.8\AA) of neutral oxygen triplet (e.g. Arellano Ferro et al., 2003; Kovtyukh et al., 2012). Yet we have to be cautious about the origin of the spectral line. As we now believe the star is enshrouded by optically thick wind which prevents direct observations on the stellar photosphere. If so, the oxygen triplet originates from the wind (or the “pseudo-photosphere”) rather than the genuine stellar photosphere.

Another indirect evidence is the expansion velocity of the outflows. Despite the difference in the driving mechanisms of stellar wind, the expansion velocity of the mass-loss in general increases with stellar luminosity because of stronger radiative pressure exerted on the dust grains which in turn drive the gas outwards (Habing & Olofsson, 2003). Also, for more luminous stars, the kinetic energy barrier for materials to escape from stellar gravity is also higher, resulting in larger outflow velocity. For AGB stars, the outflow velocity is typically $\lesssim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (e.g. Olofsson et al., 1993; Gussie & Taylor, 1994; Chen et al., 2001; Marshall et al., 2004; Bladh & Höfner, 2012). In contrast, the expansion velocity of the circumstellar materials ejected from IRC+10420 is found to be $\gtrsim 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, as estimated from the spectra and maps of ^{12}CO rotational transitions (Knapp & Morris, 1985; Oudmaijer et al., 1996; Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Quintana-Lacaci et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009; Teyssier et al., 2012); maps of OH masers (Bowers, 1984; Nedoluha & Bowers, 1992a); spectra and maps from ^{28}SiO thermal emission (Olofsson et al., 1982; Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). Figure 1.5, as taken from Figure 5 of Teyssier et al. (2012), shows an example including a set of high-spectral resolution spectra in CO. The line profiles in general span its width from around 40 km s^{-1} to 110 km s^{-1} , and centre at the systemic velocity of around 75 km s^{-1} . Therefore the outflow velocity is interpreted as roughly 35 km s^{-1} . The outflow velocities near the surface of IRC+10420 are even higher. For example, the double-peaked $\text{H}\alpha$ emission profile shows an outflow velocity of $\sim 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as inferred by fitting the measured Doppler velocities of the minima between the double peak in $\text{H}\alpha$ profiles, and the inferred position along the line of sight, with an arc-like geometrical model proposed by Humphreys et al. (2002). These all support the speculation that IRC+10420 is much more massive and luminous than AGB stars, and should be among the region of supergiants on the top of the H-R diagram for stars of its spectral type.

On the weight of available evidence as presented, we adopt the distance of IRC+10420 to be among the larger values between 4 and 5.8 kpc. The general

Figure 1.5: High-spectral resolution ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO spectra of IRC+10420 taken in April and October 2010 (Taken from Figure 5 of Teysier et al., 2012). The line profiles generally span from $\lesssim 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to $\gtrsim 110 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, about the systemic velocity (red vertical dashed line) of $\approx 75 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. The envelope expansion velocity is therefore estimated to be about $\gtrsim 35 \text{ km s}^{-1}$.

consensus for the distance to IRC+10420 is 5 kpc (e.g. Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009; Tiffany et al., 2010). If the distance is adopted to be 5 kpc from the Earth, then the inferred luminosity of the star will be very high. The apparent visual magnitude of IRC+10420, m_V , is found to be 11.0 (ASAS catalogue, Pojmanski, 1997); and extinction at visual band is roughly in the range $6.5 < A_V < 7.0$ (Humphreys et al., 2002). At the assumed distance of 5 kpc, the absolute visual magnitude would be $-9.49 < M_V < -8.99$, consistent with Klochkova et al. (2002)’s result of $M_V = -9.5 \pm 0.4$. Hence, the luminosity would be ranging from $L = 10^{5.53} L_\odot = 3.39 \times 10^5 L_\odot$ to $10^{5.73} L_\odot = 5.37 \times 10^5 L_\odot$.

1.3 Evolutionary Status of IRC+10420

Due to the ambiguity of the spectral class, the classification of IRC+10420’s nature and evolutionary status is not a trivial task. Based on the spectral type inferred from the (ill-defined) “effective temperature”, IRC+10420 is currently classified as a very rare type of massive evolved star known as yellow hypergiant (YHG). YHGs are located between luminous blue variables (LBVs) and red supergiants (RSGs) on the H-R diagram and they are generally found to be dynamically unstable (de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen, 1997; de Jager et al., 2001). Thorough review on the YHGs can be found in de Jager (1998), recent observations are summarized in Humphreys (2007); Oudmaijer et al. (2009) and recent theoretical progress is provided by de Jager et al. (2001); Stothers (2012); Nieuwenhuijzen et al. (2012) and references therein. Despite the similarities in the apparent spectral type and luminosity, the evolutionary stage (whether evolving in general bluewards from RSG stage to luminous blue variables or more evolved stages, or in general redwards from the main sequence to RSG stage) and temporal variation in the spectral type in timescale of decades (i.e. “bouncing” redwards and bluewards due to stellar instability) vary among

individual objects (Oudmaijer et al., 2009).

For IRC+10420, it is currently believed to be a post-RSG recently evolving bluewards (i.e. to the left of the H-R diagram) from RSG phase, eventually to possibly a luminous blue variable (LBV), Wolf-Rayet (WR) star and/or explode as a supernova (SN). IRC+10420 is thought to be a post-RSG because of the complex circumstellar environment with huge amount of dust and gas. It is indicative of a more evolved stage than RSG because the mass is supposed to be ejected from the central star during the RSG phase (Oudmaijer et al., 2009). Numerous studies have directly imaged the complex structures and prodigious ejecta around IRC+10420 (e.g. Kastner & Weintraub, 1995; Humphreys et al., 1997; Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009). If the star is evolving off the main sequence redward to RSG phase, crossing YHG region on the H-R diagram for the first time, then it is unlikely to possess such a large amount of dust and gas in the circumstellar ejecta.

While IRC+10420 has shown post-RSG properties and is evolving in general bluewards, we do not know for sure if its effective temperature keeps increasing all the time because there were examples (e.g. HR8752, ρ Cas, see also Figure 1.1) showing “bouncing” motions between the yellow transition phase and RSG phase during which the mass-loss rate varied in an episodic manner (de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen, 1997; de Jager, 1998; de Jager et al., 2001).

IRC+10420 is found to exhibit temporal blueward evolution with timescale of decades. OH masers (for all 1612, 1665, 1667 MHz) have been clearly detected around IRC+10420 (e.g. Benson et al., 1979; Mutel et al., 1979; Reid et al., 1979; Bowers, 1984; Nedoluha & Bowers, 1992b; Sylvester et al., 1997; Nakashima & Deguchi, 2003) but to date, there is no detectable maser in H₂O (Nyman et al., 1986), ²⁸SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) (Dickinson et al., 1978; Nyman et al., 1998; Nakashima & Deguchi, 2003) or ²⁸SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (Dick-

inson et al., 1978; Nyman et al., 1986, 1998). As ^{28}SiO and H_2O masers are formed closer to the stellar surface than OH masers (Trigilio et al., 2006), the lack of ^{28}SiO and H_2O masers and the presence of OH masers are consistent with the idea that the photospheric temperature has increased, which dissociate molecules in the region where ^{28}SiO and H_2O masers may form, while OH masers still persist because the outflow was ejected when the star was cooler (Mutel et al., 1979; Zijlstra et al., 2001). Mutel et al. (1979) predicted that “fossil” OH masers will eventually disappear as the last portion of relatively cool outflows have left stellar vicinity. As Mutel et al. (1979) argued, if the star is indeed evolving redwards, then a decreased photospheric temperature should allow H_2O and ^{28}SiO molecules to exist in recent outflows and corresponding masers should have been detected.

However, despite the blueward change in the apparent spectral type indicating an increase in the temperature of the “pseudo-photosphere”, we cannot definitely conclude whether IRC+10420 itself (but not the wind) is evolving redwards or bluewards. As Humphreys et al. (2002) mentioned, the intrinsic stellar properties (revealed by the spectral type and photospheric temperatures) may exhibit completely independent evolution with that of the detached, opaque wind ejected long time ago. For an unusual example, it is possible that IRC+10420 is indeed an even hotter star than its currently inferred mid A-type and evolving redward back to RSG. As the opaque wind becomes optically thinner, the still-hotter stellar photospheric will lead to an increase in the “apparent” effective temperature.

Assuming the distance estimate is correct, then IRC+10420 must be among the very few objects in the transition from RSG phase to much hotter objects like the LBVs or WR stars. As observed in other YHG, IRC+10420 may have already been, or will be, experiencing “bouncing” in redward and blueward loops on the H-R diagram, while maintaining roughly the same luminosity, before it eventually evolves into the final stage of evolution. It is

thought that massive stars would lose more than half of their mass as they evolve away from the main sequence due to dynamical instability (Stothers & Chin, 1996, 2001). As available evidence suggest IRC+10420 is evolving in the blueward loop, and it is also one of the few stars with detectable circumstellar envelope (Oudmaijer et al., 2009) (the only other example is the disputable YHG candidate AFGL2343 = HD 179821), it is very likely that the star is post-RSG. Expanding at $\sim 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, the circumstellar envelope of 10^4 AU suggests a dynamical timescale of a few thousand years. So IRC+10420 should have evolved off from RSG quite recently. Therefore the circumstellar envelope of this star provides us a unique opportunity to capture the blueward evolution shortly after RSG phase, and may provide hints to its future evolution (e.g. Tiffany et al., 2010). However, our understanding of the circumstellar environment around this star is still poor.

Chapter 2

Circumstellar Environment of IRC+10420

Studies of the circumstellar envelope of evolved stars provide us information about their recent mass-loss history. In particular, we can infer the relative abundances of different molecular species and the physical parameters (such as gas density and temperature) of the circumstellar envelope. The former provides important additional clues to the evolutionary status of the star, and the latter allows us to trace its mass-loss history.

2.1 Chemistry

The circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 is oxygen-rich (i.e. C/O ratio less than unity). First, intense OH maser emissions at 1612, 1665 and 1667 MHz have been detected towards its inner envelope. (e.g. Benson et al., 1979; Mutel et al., 1979; Reid et al., 1979; Bowers, 1984; Nedoluha & Bowers, 1992b; Sylvester et al., 1997; Nakashima & Deguchi, 2003). Because oxygen atoms are easily locked by carbon atoms to form CO molecules, the presence

of OH requires an overabundance of atomic oxygen with respect to atomic carbon and therefore indicates an oxygen-rich envelope (Habing, 1990). Second, Quintana-Lacaci et al. (2007) has conducted an extensive survey for different carbon- or oxygen-bearing molecules around various evolved stars including IRC+10420. They concluded that the envelope of IRC+10420 is oxygen-rich based on the comparisons of relative molecular abundances, as calculated from the intensities of various molecular transitions at mm-wavelengths (e.g. ^{13}CO , C^{18}O , SiO , ^{29}SiO , SiS , HCN , HNC , CS , etc.), with AGB stars of carbon-rich and oxygen-rich chemistries. Apart from OH, oxygen-bearing molecules such as SiO are expected to be abundant in the inner envelope of IRC+10420.

2.2 Circumstellar Dust

Ever since the first spectral study of the star, IRC+10420 has been known to be surrounded by copious dust. Humphreys et al. (1973) detected huge infrared excess (above the expected photospheric emission) at around $11\mu\text{m}$ and $20\mu\text{m}$. Forrest et al. (1979) and Jones et al. (1993) also identified a spectral feature at about $18\mu\text{m}$, that is now commonly attributed to amorphous silicate Si–O stretching and O–Si–O bending modes (Draine & Lee, 1984; Henning, 2010). These molecules cannot form at the relatively high temperatures of the stellar photosphere, and therefore their spectral features indicate the presence of a circumstellar envelope rich in molecular gas. The spectral energy distribution (SED) also provides us information about the inner structure and kinetic temperature of the circumstellar envelope. For instance, modelling of IRC+10420’s SED suggests the circumstellar dust envelope around the star probably consist of double shell. Oudmaijer et al. (1996) show that a single cool shell with an inner radius of $0''.23 = 1150 \text{ AU}$ at the temperature of 400 K, outer radius of $202'' = 1.01 \times 10^6 \text{ AU}$ at temperature of 20 K and a mass-loss rate of $9 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ fits the SED well in the spectral ranges of

$\lambda < 1.6\mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda > 10\mu\text{m}$. They also showed that just this single cool shell fails to explain all the emission between $1.6\mu\text{m}$ and $10\mu\text{m}$. Rather, in addition to a cool outer shell, Oudmaijer et al. (1996) invoked an inner, hot (1000 K) dust shell (between $0''.042 = 210 \text{ AU}$ and $0''.23 = 1150 \text{ AU}$) of mass-loss rate $7.0 \times 10^{-5} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ so as to produce a satisfactory fit to the entire spectral range. The properties of the two inferred dust shells imply that the mass loss rate of IRC+10420 must have dropped dramatically by more than a factor of 10 over the last 135 years, and may have entirely ceased over the past 25 yrs. (Note the listed numerical values assumed the distance to us to be 5 kpc. If other distance is adopted, then the shell radii and mass-loss rates should be scaled proportionally.) In their model, the outer radius of the cool shell is where the dust temperature has dropped to 20 K, and is calculated to be huge (up to nearly 5 pc) (Oudmaijer et al., 1996). Similar conclusions, with an inner hot dust shell connecting to an outer cool dust shell and similar range of fitting parameters, are also drawn by subsequent SED modelling (Blöcker et al., 1999; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

Images of the circumstellar dust provide a more straightforward view of the distribution of dust than that inferred from modelling the infrared SED. Figure 2.1 shows the infrared emission at four different wavelengths from the dust envelope around the star as imaged by Humphreys et al. (1997) and 2.2 shows the contour maps at two of the imaged wavelengths. As can be seen, the southwest and northeast part of the envelope show consistently stronger emission than other directions at all wavelengths. The distribution of mass can also be inferred from the images of dust shell. A large fraction of total emission at $10.3\mu\text{m}$ comes from the extended component (beyond $\sim 0''.5 = 2500 \text{ AU}$, up to about $1''.0 = 5000 \text{ AU}$) possibly suggests that the inner region contains much less dust than the extended component and indicates a change in mass-loss rate (Humphreys et al., 1997), given that the mid-IR emission is probably optically thin as the central star is visible.

Figure 2.1: Circumstellar dust shell directly imaged at the infrared wavelengths ($2.2 \mu\text{m}$, $8.8 \mu\text{m}$, $10.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $12.5 \mu\text{m}$) in April 1996 (Taken from Figure 6 of Humphreys et al., 1997).

Figure 2.2: Contour levels of infrared emission from the circumstellar dust around IRC+10420 at $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $10.3 \mu\text{m}$, overlaying on the *HST* optical image taken in April 1996 (Taken from Figure 9 of Humphreys et al., 1997).

Optical images of the circumstellar environment reveal scattered light from dust and preferably probe regions closer to the star. Because of high spatial resolution, optical scattered light observations provide us the greatest detail on small-scale structures. Numerous complex, small-scale structures has been imaged in the optical within the globally spherically symmetric envelope of IRC+10420. As shown in Figure 2.3, Humphreys et al. (1997) imaged IRC+10420 with the *Hubble* Space Telescope (HST) in April 1996. This image revealed a very clumpy environment around IRC+10420, with larger-scale shells and smaller-scale condensations, knots, arcs or jet-like features. In particular, Humphreys et al. (1997) detected a number of dense and clumpy (fan-like) features towards the southwest direction which may be associated with those traced in ^{12}CO emission (as will be discussed in Section 2.3). The identified small-scale structures are summerized in Figure 2.4 schematically. Tiffany et al. (2010) followed up with the second epoch of HST observation in March 2008 and, as shown in Figure 2.5, they also identified many condensations, knots and arcs (at least up to $2''$ from the star). These images show clearly

that although the envelope of IRC+10420 is globally spherically symmetric, it also shows localized small-scale structures and is particularly clumpy along the southwest and northeast direction.

Some of the clumps are associated with the previous epoch as observed by Humphreys et al. (1997) and therefore by comparing the relative shift in position of these clumps, Tiffany et al. (2010) are able to derive the transverse motion in the plane of sky. They found that the transverse velocity spans a wide range, from the detectability limit of $\sim 15 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to more than 200 km s^{-1} . Combining with the radial velocities derived from the slit-spectroscopy on some of the substructures (Humphreys et al., 2002), Tiffany et al. (2010) determined the three-dimensional kinematics for 40 knots. They found that these knots generally move in a relatively high transverse velocities of $\sim 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ compared to the wind outflow velocity around 40 km s^{-1} . In addition, all these knots have much lower radial velocities of less than 20 km s^{-1} as derived from Humphreys et al. (2002). Therefore, Tiffany et al. (2010) concluded that the outflow from IRC+10420 should be nearly pole-on.

2.3 Circumstellar Molecular Gas

Although optical and infrared images provide us high spatial resolution to investigate the detailed structures in the circumstellar envelope, they do not provide good estimate of the global mass-loss because of circumstellar and interstellar dust extinction, and also the fact that part of the emission is scattered light from dust. CO molecules, commonly accepted as the best tracer of molecular gas, can probe the recent global mass-loss history (with typical timescales of few thousands years) from an evolved star. ^{12}CO is the best tracer of molecular hydrogen (H_2) for a few reasons. First, it is the most abundant molecular species after H_2 (e.g. Combes, 1991). Second, the lowest transition, ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$), has a critical density of $n_{\text{crit}} = A_{10}/C_{10} =$

Figure 2.3: Direct optical image of the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 as observed by the *HST*. This pseudo-coloured image is a combined image at the blue (F467M) and visual (F547M) filters (Taken from Figure 4 of Humphreys et al., 1997).

Figure 2.4: Schematic diagram for the small-scale structures identified from the *HST* optical images at the blue (F467M) and visual (F547M) filters for the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420. Structures labelled with: A and B represent the outer shell from $3''.0$ to $6''.0$; C represents the “shelf” structure between $2''.5$ and $4''.0$; D represent the multiple spherical “arc” structures located at about $1''.8$ towards the eastern side of the star, with radius roughly $0''.4$; E and F represent the “jet”-like structures roughly coincide with the diffraction spikes; and G represents the “fan”-shaped structures towards the southwest direction, spanning nearly all radii from $0''.6$ to $6''.0$. (Taken from Figure 7 of Humphreys et al., 1997).

Figure 2.5: The complex circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 has been imaged with *HST* in March 2008. Numerous small-scale structures, referred as “knots”, are identified in the envelope beyond (top panel) and within (bottom panel) a radius of $1''$ respectively. In particular, the southwest part of the envelope seems to exhibit most prominent dust-scattered emission and clumpiness, which are consistent with the infrared dust emission and the first epoch *HST* image (April 1996) as shown in Figures 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3. (Taken from Figure 2 of Tiffany et al., 2010).

$7 \times 10^{-4} / 3 \times 10^{-11} \sim 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ comparable to the density around circumstellar envelope, which allows ^{12}CO to be collisionally excited in typical circumstellar environment (e.g. Combes, 1991). Third, the Galaxy is transparent to the wavelength of ^{12}CO (2.6mm) (e.g. Combes, 1991), thus allowing us to detect the emission from the source directly. Therefore the physical parameters like molecular hydrogen gas density (n_{H_2}) and gas kinetic temperature (T_{kin}) can be derived through modelling the line profiles of ^{12}CO transition lines.

There are a number of CO observations of IRC+10420 from which the global mass-loss history and the global morphology of the envelope have been studied. Early findings only derived the mass-loss rate through single-dish line profiles. Recent interferometric studies provide us unprecedented high spatial resolution images allowing the detailed radial profiles of physical parameters (in particular the gas density), and hence the mass-loss history to be deduced accurately and compared to optical results. Since there are many parameters (such as density, kinetic temperature, molecular abundance etc.) that may contribute to the modelling of CO emission, we cannot simultaneously deduce all of the parameters in a single observation or modelling without imposing certain model assumptions. In the following subsections we will examine how the global mass-loss history of the CO-emitting envelope of IRC+10420 is deduced and each of the major underlying assumptions.

2.3.1 Single-dish CO Observation

Teyssier et al. (2006) has observed IRC+10420 in ^{12}CO and measured the single-dish line profiles at the transition $J = 6-5$ in September 2001 and February 2002 with the Caltech Submillimeter Observatory (CSO). Teyssier et al. (2006) also include the single-dish spectra for ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) as observed by Neri et al. (1998) with the IRAM 30 m telescope at Pico Veleta (PV) in October 1990, and those for ^{12}CO ($J = 3-2$) and

^{12}CO ($J = 4-3$) as observed by Oudmaijer et al. (1996) with the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope (JCMT) in June 1993 in their model to reproduce the observed line profiles.

In their model, Teyssier et al. (2006) adopt the large velocity gradient (LVG, or Sobolev) approximation (Sobolev, 1960) in which the expansion velocity is assumed to be much larger than the local velocity turbulence. This assumption is valid for the ^{12}CO envelope of IRC+10420 because the envelope expansion velocity is about 37 km s^{-1} , as inferred from the width of the line profiles, and the local turbulence velocity is about 0.2 km s^{-1} , as inferred from the smoothness of the line profiles. Under the LVG approximation, the radiative transfer is treated as a local problem and the photon will not be absorbed by molecules in the neighbouring region of the envelope along the line of sight (Kwok, 2007). The calculation of level populations can then be simplified using the escape probability method (Sobolev, 1960; Castor, 1970) which decouples the level populations from the “average radiation field intensity”. The average radiation field intensity is expressed in terms of escape probability $\beta(\tau)$ which enables the system of statistical equilibrium equations in terms of level populations to be solved iteratively.

With the model formulated by LVG approximation and the primary aim of constraining the physical conditions (i.e. the density and kinetic temperature of the gas envelope), the radial range of the envelope, molecular abundance and kinetic temperature for ^{12}CO will have to be assumed. Since high-spatial resolution images were not available at the time of single-dish observation, the inner radius of the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope can only be inferred indirectly. As we mentioned in previous section (Section 2.2), SED modelling of the dust envelope in the infrared provides us the information about the inner structure of the envelope. Teyssier et al. (2006) assumed the inner radius of $1.0 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}$ ($\sim 667 \text{ AU}$) which is consistent with the inner radius of the single dust shell ($= 1.3 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}$, assuming distance of 5 kpc) as inferred by Hrivnak et al.

(1989) who fit the infrared SED from $0.4\mu\text{m}$ to $100\mu\text{m}$. Although subsequent results generally show that there should be a hot component interior to the cool dust shell (e.g. Oudmaijer et al., 1996; Blöcker et al., 1999), the spectral lines included in Teyssier et al. (2006)'s model are more sensitive to the outer cooler envelope due to the low excitation energies of at most 116 K. In addition, we expect the majority of the mass (and hence ^{12}CO emission) should come from the much more extended cool shell instead of the compact, inner hot component. Therefore the adopted value of 1.0×10^{16} cm is a good approximation for the inner radius of low- J ^{12}CO -emitting region. The outer radius of the envelope, instead of assuming to be the photodissociation (by interstellar UV photons) radius of CO, Teyssier et al. (2006) treated it as a free parameter to be determined in modelling. The reason is that the mass-loss from the evolved star may be episodic (and indeed it is as we now understand) and therefore the extent of the CO envelope may not reach its photodissociation limit.

As Teyssier et al. (2006) mentioned, CO molecule has relatively simple chemistry in which once the chemistry of the envelope is identified, the CO molecular abundance relative to hydrogen molecules is more or less the same among envelopes of the same type. As we mentioned in Section 2.1, the envelope of IRC+10420 is identified as oxygen-rich. Therefore Teyssier et al. (2006) assumed a constant value of ^{12}CO abundance throughout the envelope. The adopted value is 3×10^{-4} which is typical for oxygen-rich envelopes (e.g. Olofsson et al., 2002).

Due to the limitation that single-dish line profiles do not contain spatial information, Teyssier et al. (2006) have adopted commonly assumed profiles to approximate the density and temperature variation in the envelope as a function of radius. Assuming the gas expands uniformly and the mass-loss rate remains constant over the entire mass-loss history, the radial gas density profile follows an inverse square law $n(r) \sim 1/r^2$. Although interferometric observations, as we will describe below, reveal that the mass-loss

rate of IRC+10420 as traced in CO has changed dramatically over time, the constant mass-loss rate assumption is still valid in inferring the approximate mass-loss rate from the star averaged over time. For the kinetic temperature, Teyssier et al. (2006) also adopted a power-law for the kinetic temperature, $T_{\text{kin}}(r) = T(10^{16} \text{ cm}) \text{ K} \cdot (r/10^{16} \text{ cm})^{-\alpha}$, as is commonly assumed for the envelope of evolved stars. For reference, the power-law index α is about $-4/3 = -1.33$ if the thermodynamics of H_2 molecules are treated as monoatomic molecules ($\gamma = 5/3$) which is valid when $T_{\text{kin}} < 300 \text{ K}$ (Goldreich & Scoville, 1976). These make the mass-loss rate, temperature scale and the power-law index as the free parameters (in addition to the outer envelope radius) to fit the line profiles.

Under the above assumptions, Teyssier et al. (2006) obtained the fit to the five ^{12}CO spectra with the outer radius of $4.5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$ (30000 AU, $6''.0$), which is consistent with the spatial extent of the optical *HST* image (Humphreys et al., 1997). A very high mass-loss rate of $\dot{M} = 3 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$, as compared to typical AGB/post-AGB stars for which $\dot{M} \sim 10^{-7}-10^{-5} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ (e.g. Bujarrabal et al., 1989; Teyssier et al., 2006), is also obtained. The mass-loss rate is comparable to the previous estimate by Knapp & Morris (1985), who modelled the ^{12}CO line profile in a similar manner but only for the lowest transition, ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$). Teyssier et al. (2006) also infer a high kinetic temperature profile of $T_{\text{kin}}(r) = 1000 \text{ K} \cdot (r/10^{16} \text{ cm})^{-1.2}$ ($= 63.1 \text{ K} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-1.2}$) in order to explain the intensity of ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$). As a reference, for other typical AGB/post-AGB stars, Teyssier et al. (2006) found much lower values of $T_{\text{kin}}(10^{16} \text{ cm}) \sim 20-400 \text{ K}$.

The above single-dish modelling together show that the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope of IRC+10420 is much denser and hotter than those of typical AGB/post-AGB stars. In addition, we learn from single-dish spectra that the size of the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope of IRC+10420 is comparable to that seen in the optical.

2.3.2 Mass-loss History from CO Interferometry

The most detailed picture of the mass loss from IRC+10420 over the last few thousand years comes from modelling of CO maps of the circumstellar envelope. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) have imaged the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 as traced in ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$); and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) have also imaged the envelope in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$). Here we summarize the global distribution of gas as a function of radius as well as smaller-scale structures imaged by both Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009). To infer the physical conditions of the circumstellar envelope as traced in ^{12}CO , both Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) modelled the radiative transfer of both ^{12}CO transitions so as to reproduce the respective radial profiles of brightness temperature. We will therefore examine the motivations, assumptions and inferred mass-loss history of their models for the imaged ^{12}CO -emitting envelope.

The global geometry of the molecular gas envelope as traced in ^{12}CO follows spherical symmetry. As shown in Figures 2.6 and 2.7 respectively, the channel maps for ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission show that the shape of ^{12}CO -emitting region appears to be circular in the (projected) two-dimensional maps (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007). At velocities progressively further away from the systemic value (i.e. the central velocity channel), the size of ^{12}CO emission shrinks in size at the extreme velocities. For a spherically symmetric and expanding envelope, different velocity channels reflects different cross-sectional layers of the circumstellar envelope being observed. When the LSR velocity moves away from the systemic to the extreme, the plane of observation will also move from the plane on sky across the source, to the front or rear of the envelope and that the projected size of emission should shrink. Therefore the entire set of ^{12}CO channel maps together resemble a roughly spherically symmetric envelope.

Figure 2.6: Channel maps of ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) emission from the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 with the PdBI interferometric and IRAM 30 m single-dish data combined. In each panel, LSR velocities in km s^{-1} are indicated on the top-left corner. Synthesized beam of size $3''.1 \times 2''.6$ ($\text{PA} = 77^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-right corner of the figure. The sensitivity is $\sigma \sim 0.12$ K. Each contour is $5 \times \sigma$ (Taken from Figure 3 of Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

Figure 2.7: Channel maps of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission from the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 with the PdBI interferometric and IRAM 30 m single-dish data combined. In each panel, LSR velocities in km s^{-1} are indicated on the top-left corner. Synthesized beam of size $1''.5 \times 1''.3$ ($\text{PA} = 120^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-right corner of the figure. The sensitivity is $\sigma \sim 0.14$ K. Each contour is $5 \times \sigma$ (Taken from Figure 2 of Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

Figure 2.8: Dashed lines represents the azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profiles of ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission as observed with the PdBI at the central channel (corresponding to the systemic velocity of 75 km s^{-1}). Solid line represents the respective brightness temperature profiles as predicted in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)’s ^{12}CO model. (Taken from Figure 10 of Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

In addition, the channel map at the systemic velocity shows emission in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) that peaks at a ring-like structure located at a radius from the star of around $1''$ (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007). This indicates a central depression or hollow shell with a radius of $1''$. The central depression is more prominent in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) than in ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) possibly due to the higher angular resolution in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$). These suggest the ^{12}CO molecules are distributed in a detached, hollow shell at $1''$. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 2.8, the azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profiles revealed a local minimum in the ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission between $\sim 2'' - 3''$, and a secondary peak which Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) referred as a “hump” at around $4'' - 5''$.

Apart from the general structure of the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope, small-scale structures are also identified. At the systemic velocity of $\sim 74 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) have detected a strong, clumpy emission towards the southwest direction up to $\sim 3''$, consistent with Humphreys et al. (1997)'s optical image which show a series of southwest fan-like structures from around $0''.6$ to $\sim 6''$. Also, as shown in Figure 2.9, closer inspection reveals a small velocity gradient across velocity channels from southwest to northeast along an axis of $\text{PA} \sim 70^\circ$ of magnitude $\sim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$, possibly suggesting an embedded disk or bipolar outflow for the inner structure of the envelope (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) independently measured ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission using the Submillimeter Array (SMA), with two configurations corresponding to high and low spatial resolution respectively. Figure 2.10 shows the low spatial resolution maps of Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) with similar sensitivity (of $\sigma \sim 0.13 \text{ K}$) as in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s PdBI map of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) (of $\sigma \sim 0.14 \text{ K}$, see Figure 2.7). These maps show that the molecular gas envelope traced in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) exhibit a global spherical symmetry with a spatial extent of nearly $8''$. Higher spatial resolution maps with a relatively large sensitivity of $\sigma \sim 1.1 \text{ K}$, as shown in Figure 2.11, reveal a very clumpy ^{12}CO -emitting envelope around the star. Since these high spatial resolution map is only sensitive to bright emission, we can see more clearly the hollow shell of emission in the inner envelope of radii $1'' - 2''$; and a nearly detached secondary shell of emission in the outer envelope of radii $3'' - 6''$. The azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profile of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$), as shown in Figure 2.12, also reveal a general trend similar to that found in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) – a detached hollow shell at $1''$, local emission minimum at $\sim 2'' - 3''$, and a secondary peak in emission at $\sim 4'' - 5''$.

The high spatial resolution of interferometric images enables us to infer more accurately the mass-loss history of IRC+10420 as a function of radius

Figure 2.9: Position-velocity (PV) diagram of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission along an axis of position angle $\text{PA} = 72^\circ$ that passes through the peak emission across the channel maps shown in Figure 2.7. The offset in vertical axis represents the angular distance from northeast (low offset) to southwest (high offset). Contours are plotted at an interval of 2.24 K up to 15.68 K, and 16.80 K, 17.36 K, 17.58 K and 17.92 K. The systemic velocity and position of the central star are marked by the vertical and horizontal lines respectively. Therefore there is an apparent positive velocity gradient from the southwest to northeast. (Taken from Figure 7 of Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

Figure 2.10: Channel maps of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission from the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 imaged with the (lower spatial resolution) SMA compact configurations. In each panel, LSR velocities in km s^{-1} are indicated on the top-left corner. Synthesized beam of size $3''.44 \times 3''.12$ ($\text{PA} = 46^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-left corner of the figure. The sensitivity is $\sigma \sim 0.13$ K. Each contour is $10 \times \sigma$ (Taken from Figure 3 of Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

Figure 2.11: Channel maps of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission from the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 imaged with the (higher spatial resolution) SMA, combining data from compact and extended configurations. In each panel, LSR velocities in km s^{-1} are indicated on the top-left corner. Synthesized beam of size $1''.44 \times 1''.12$ ($\text{PA} = 46^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-left corner of the figure. The sensitivity is $\sigma \sim 1.1 \text{ K}$. Each contour is $3 \times \sigma$ (Taken from Figure 4 of Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

Figure 2.12: Dotted line represents the azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profile of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission as observed with the SMA at the central channel (corresponding to the systemic velocity of 75 km s^{-1}). Solid line represents the predicted brightness temperature profile in Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009)'s model explaining both ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission. (Taken from Figure 13 of Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

instead of merely a global average history as from single-dish observations. Through modelling the radiative transfer of ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission in order to simultaneously fit the radial brightness temperature profiles of both transition lines, the radial profiles for molecular gas density and hence the mass-loss rate can be inferred (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

As we have demonstrated previously, the ^{12}CO envelope exhibits a global spherically symmetric geometry. The radiative transfer model therefore assumes spherical symmetry for the envelope. As motivated by the radial brightness temperature profiles which show, in addition to the primary peak at around $1''$, a secondary peak at around $4'' - 5''$, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) assume the mass-loss from IRC+10420 as two distinct episodes with constant mass-loss rates and uniform gas expansion. In between the episodes, the mass-loss rate is assumed to be essentially zero for simplicity of the model. Therefore the radial gas density profile can be parameterized as inverse square law, i.e. $n(r) = \dot{M} / (4\pi V_{\text{exp}} r^2)$, similarly to Teyssier et al. (2006) – despite that there is a respective inverse square law for each mass-loss episode.

Similar to Teyssier et al. (2006), Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) assumed a constant ^{12}CO abundance of 3×10^{-4} which is typical for oxygen-rich envelope. As for the radial kinetic temperature profile, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) combine (1) their spatially resolved radial brightness temperature profiles and (2) radial line profiles ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$)/ ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) with (3) the single-dish line intensity profiles up to ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$) (excitation energy = 116 K) taken by Teyssier et al. (2006). Under the same assumptions as in Teyssier et al. (2006)'s modelling who only includes the single-dish profiles without spatial information, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) deduce a much higher temperature profile than Teyssier et al. (2006). Their best-fit parameters are all summarized in Table 2.1.

As motivated similarly as Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) also model the radial brightness temperature profiles with two distinct episodes of mass loss, each having a constant mass-loss rate. On the other hand, Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) deduce the ^{12}CO abundance and kinetic temperature in a different approach. First, instead of assuming a typical value for ^{12}CO abundance as in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) treated abundance as a free parameter to fit both radial brightness profiles from interferometric and line profiles from single-dish observations. In addition, instead of approximating with a power-law, Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) calculated the heating and cooling processes of the CO molecular gas directly. In their thermodynamic calculation, CO molecules were assumed to be heated only through momentum transfer during collisions with radiatively accelerated dust grains (under the high radiation pressure from the luminous central star) and cooled in two ways – (1) molecular emissions of (presumably) only ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO and (2) adiabatic expansion of the gas. As we summarized in Table 2.1, the calculated temperature profile by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) is significantly lower than those derived by Teyssier et al. (2006) and Teyssier et al. (2012). The former profile gives a kinetic temperature of < 80 K at 10^{17} cm, while the later two give 230 K and 170 K at that radius respectively. Although Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) included some input physics in the calculation, as they have pointed out, their calculation does not consider the coupling of dust and gas and any non-thermal heating process (such as shocks, as hinted by high outflow velocity and the ^{28}SiO emission as described in Section 2.4). In addition, the modelling to single-dish ^{12}CO line profiles includes transitions from ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) up to ^{12}CO ($J = 16-15$), covering a wide range of excitation energies from a few K to ~ 750 K (Teyssier et al., 2012). Thus these transitions can probe both the high and low temperature regions at the inner and outer envelopes respectively. Therefore the power-law temperature profile seems to be a better approximation of the actual gas kinetic temperature of the envelope. In particular, Teyssier et al. (2012)'s latest

temperature profile as deduced from high- J transitions of CO should be more accurate than that previously deduced by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) who only include transitions up to ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$), corresponding to a maximum excitation energy of only 116 K, way below and insensitive to the high kinetic temperature (at least 700 K) at the innermost region of the inner CO shell.

Under the above assumptions, both Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) independently fit the radial brightness temperature profiles with a model consisting of two distinct ^{12}CO shells, corresponding to two separated mass-loss episodes. The earlier mass-loss episode, which can be traced back to more than 4000 years ago, has a lower mass-loss rate while the more recent episode has a higher mass-loss rate. The two episodes are separated by a quiescent period of very low mass loss. Also, to explain the centrally depressed emission, both models suggest that the mass-loss probably has ceased over the past 200–300 years.

In Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s model, the inner (more recently ejected) ^{12}CO shell spans the radial range from 2.5×10^{16} cm (1670 AU) to 1.24×10^{17} cm (8270 AU) and has a mass-loss rate of $3 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$; while the outer (older) ^{12}CO shell spans from 2.2×10^{17} cm (14700 AU) to 5.2×10^{17} cm (34700 AU) and has a mass-loss rate of $1.2 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$. The mass-loss rate as a function of radius from star is shown in Figure 2.13. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) deduce, by adopting a constant expansion velocity for each mass-loss episode (i.e. ^{12}CO shell), that the outer shell corresponds to an earlier mass-loss episode started 6000 years ago, lasting for 3800 years, and the inner shell corresponds to a recent episode started 1000 years ago and ceased 200 years ago.

On the other hand, Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009), computed a lower kinetic temperature profile rather than simply assuming a power law, found that a higher mass-loss rate (i.e. molecular density) and a lower ^{12}CO abundance than

Figure 2.13: Mass-loss history of IRC+10420 as modelled by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) to explain the brightness temperatures of ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) as a function of radius from star. Given the mass-loss rate at each radius, the mass-loss history as a function of time in the past can be inferred by adopting a constant expansion velocity, V_{exp} . For the inner shell, corresponding to a more recent mass-loss episode, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) adopt $V_{\text{exp,in}} = 37 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ from model fit and infer that this episode spanned from 1000 years ago to 200 years ago; and for the outer shell (an earlier episode), $V_{\text{exp,out}} = 25 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and the episode spanned from 6000 years ago to 2200 years ago (Taken from Figure 10 of Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007).

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) are required to fit both single-dish line profiles and interferometry maps. The inner ^{12}CO shell as derived by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) spans from 3.5×10^{16} cm (2330 AU) to 1.5×10^{17} cm (10000 AU) and has a mass-loss rate of $9 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ (triple of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)’s model); the outer shell spans from 1.85×10^{17} cm (12300 AU) to 5×10^{17} cm (33300 AU) and has a mass-loss rate of $7 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ (about 6 times the Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)’s model). If we assume the expansion velocity to be constant at 38 km s^{-2} (as estimated from the line profiles), then this model suggests the following mass-loss history. An “older” phase of high mass-loss occurred from about 4170 years ago, until around 1540 years ago (lasted for around 2630 years). Then the mass-loss from the star essentially ceased for nearly 300 years until the more recent phase of high mass-loss rate started 1250 years ago. The central depression, as Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009)’s model suggests, is due to the dramatic fall in the mass-loss rate very recently, less than 300 years ago. The mass-loss history is qualitatively consistent with that suggested by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)’s model in which there is a phase of lower mass-loss further in the past and a phase of recent, high mass-loss period. Also, in between the two mass-loss episodes, and in the very recent past, the star exhibits quiescent periods of essentially zero mass-loss, leading to a “gap” in the modelled density distribution and the centrally depressed envelope respectively. If we use the higher mass-loss rate estimate by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009), then the wind opacity during the major mass-loss episode would be opaque enough ($\tau \sim 3$, derivation similar to Appendix B) to produce a “pseudo-photosphere”. Therefore, IRC+10420 is capable of producing wind that is opaque enough to cause temporal change in the apparent spectral type.

2.4 SiO Molecules

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) have mapped, as we will show in Figure 4.3,

the spatial distribution of ^{28}SiO molecules for the transition ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$), which are tracers of high gas density due to relatively high critical density of $\sim 10^{5.5} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ compared to ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) of $\sim 10^{3.3} - 10^{4.1} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respectively (Schöier et al., 2005). As molecular SiO gases are expected to condense onto dust grain at temperatures of about 900 K (Gail et al., 2013), essentially all SiO molecules should be depleted onto dust grains at radius beyond 10^{16} cm ($\sim 10^3 \text{ AU}$) around evolved stars (e.g. Bujarrabal et al., 1989; Lucas et al., 1992). The spatial distribution low- J SiO emission should therefore be very compact, if not unresolved. Surprisingly, however, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found that ^{28}SiO thermal emission that was spatially extended up to around $4''.0$, or 20000 AU (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). A ring-like enhancement in emission was observed near $1''.50$ (7500 AU) (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). Apart from IRC+10420, the only other example, AFGL2343 (HD 179821, a YHG candidate), is also known to exhibit spatially extended emission in SiO (^{29}SiO) (Quintana-Lacaci et al., 2008). In both cases, the ^{28}SiO emission is spatially extended with an overall size of roughly 20000 AU. Furthermore, AFGL2343 also exhibits an enhanced ring of ^{28}SiO emission at radii near $\sim 10000 \text{ AU}$ and the emission close to the central star, within $\sim 10000 \text{ AU}$, is comparatively depressed.

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) treated the radial range and the kinetic temperature of the ^{28}SiO -emitting shell as free parameters in their model – for which we will discuss in detail in Section 5.3. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found that an excitation temperature of $T_{\text{ex}} \approx 55 \text{ K}$ is required to reproduce the observed peak intensity (brightness temperature of $\sim 20 \text{ K}$) in the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) channel maps (as shown in Figure 5.4, which will be further discussed in Section 5.3). They found that ^{28}SiO emission mainly comes from a detached ring between $1''.20$ (6000 AU) and $1''.87$ (9333 AU) in order to fit the channel maps, as will be shown in Figure 4.3. By assuming that the gas emitting in ^{28}SiO also emits in ^{12}CO , Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) attributed a constant mass-loss rate of $3.6 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (obtained by modelling the

single-dish ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) line profile taken by Neri et al. (1998)) to the ^{28}SiO shell. Also assuming a constant expansion velocity and free expansion of the gas, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) adopt an inverse square law for the gas density within the radial range of their postulated ^{28}SiO shell. The density within the ^{28}SiO shell ranges from $0.89 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $2.15 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This profile is way below the critical density of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) ($3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) (Schöier et al., 2005). As the assumed gas density is so low, the only way to get a high ^{28}SiO column density required for the observed emission is to assume a high relative ^{28}SiO abundance of 2×10^{-5} , which is typically found in the inner envelope within the dust condensation radius ($\sim 10^{15} \text{ cm}$) around massive evolved stars (e.g. Bujarrabal et al., 1989).

The reason for the strong ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission at a large distance from the IRC+10420 beyond dust condensation radius is not understood yet. In order to explain the existence of ^{28}SiO gas at extended radii, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) and Quintana-Lacaci et al. (2008) have proposed that the SiO emission from the winds of both IRC+10420 and AFGL2343 originates from a region where a faster-moving part of the wind ejected more recently by the star is ploughing into a slower-moving part of the wind ejected at an earlier time, creating a large-scale shock. Such a shock will compress the gas in the shocked region, thus enhancing the molecular gas density, and/or heat the gas to an elevated temperature. SiO molecules will be evaporated from the silicate dust grains and strongly emit if the gas density is above the critical values for the respective transition. This is currently the most plausible mechanism proposed to explain the origin of intense SiO emission at radii of tens of thousands of AU from the central hypergiants. Moreover, evidence in support for shocks chemistry and high density regions in the envelope of IRC+10420 has been observed. For example, Teyssier et al. (2012) detect H_2O and NH_3 spectral lines which are typically found in shocked regions; Quintana-Lacaci et al. (2008) also report the detection of high density tracers such as HCN and higher ^{28}SiO transitions; OH masers have been mapped indicative of dense

regions around the inner envelope (e.g. Bowers, 1984; Nedoluha & Bowers, 1992b).

For the ^{12}CO observations which were done after Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s ^{28}SiO observation, the regions of ^{12}CO -emitting shells do not coincide with the speculated ^{28}SiO shell. The radial range of the ^{28}SiO shell, including the location of the peak in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission, is between $1''.20$ (6000 AU) and $1''.87$ (9333 AU). This radial range corresponds to the outer edge of the inner ^{12}CO shell and even part of the low density “gap” (parameterized as zero density between $1''.65 = 8270$ AU and $2''.83 = 14700$ AU) in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s model, and also corresponds to the outer region of the inner ^{12}CO shell in Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009)'s model. If Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s model is correct, then the region of the low density ^{12}CO “gap” has an upper mass-loss rate limit of $\sim 10^{-5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which means the maximum possible density of $\sim 300 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. It seems to be impossible to provide sufficient density for the excitation of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (critical density $\sim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). In order to solve the puzzle in the extended ^{28}SiO emission, and the inconsistency between ^{28}SiO and ^{12}CO emissions, we need to better constrain the physical conditions such as gas density, kinetic temperature and relative abundance of SiO. We therefore need to observe ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) to get the line intensity ratio which allows us to infer the optical thickness of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions and distinguish between high and low density regions. Combining the intensity profiles of individual transitions, we may deduce the relevant physical parameters such as density and abundance by radiative transfer modelling.

In this thesis, we report interferometric observations of IRC+10420 in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) that, when combined with those in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) previously reported by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001), allow us to better constrain the physical parameters of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions through radiative transfer modelling. In Chapter 3, we mention about the observation.

In Chapter 4, we present the maps and radial brightness temperature profiles of our observed ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission from IRC+10420. Then, we will investigate the possible ranges of physical parameters and model the radiative transfer using different physical conditions for IRC+10420's circumstellar envelope in Chapter 5. Finally we will also discuss the plausible physical interpretations in Chapter 6.

Model	Shell	R_{in}	R_{out}	\dot{M}	T_{17}	α	V_{exp}	$f_{^{12}\text{CO}}$
(year)		(10^{17} cm)		(M_{\odot}/yr)	(K)		(km/s)	(10^{-4})
C(2001)	SiO	0.90	1.40	3.6×10^{-4}	~ 55	N/A	35	N/A
T(2006)		0.10	5.00	3.0×10^{-4}	63.1	1.2	37	3.0
C(2007)	inner	0.25	1.24	3.0×10^{-4}	230	1.2	37	3.0
	outer	2.20	5.20	1.2×10^{-4}	100	0.8	25	
T(2012)	inner	0.25	1.24	3.0×10^{-4}	170	1.2	37	3.0
					230	0.8		
	outer	2.20	5.20	1.2×10^{-4}	100	0.8	25	
D(2009)	inner	0.35	1.50	9.0×10^{-4}	$\lesssim 80$	~ 0.5	38	1.0
	outer	1.85	6.00	7.0×10^{-4}				

Table 2.1: Model parameters including the inner (R_{in}) and outer (R_{out}) radii, mass-loss rate (\dot{M}), kinetic temperature at 10^{17} cm (T_{17}), power law index (α), envelope expansion velocity (V_{exp}) and molecular ^{12}CO abundance relative to H_2 ($f_{^{12}\text{CO}}$) that fit the corresponding CO line profiles or maps (see Section 2.3) observed by Teyssier et al. (2006) [T(2006)], Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) [C(2007)], Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) [D(2009)] and Teyssier et al. (2012) [T(2012)]. There is no analytical form for the kinetic temperature profile calculated by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) and the listed values are just approximations. The parameters inferred by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) [C(2001)] to fit the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) maps are also included for comparison of the radial ranges, for which we will explain in Section 2.4 the inconsistency with CO models.

Chapter 3

Observations and Data Reduction

3.1 VLA Observation

IRC+10420 was observed by Dr. Dinh-Van-Trung and Dr. Jeremy Lim with the Karl G. Jansky Very Large Array (VLA) on 19 April 2010, before the start of this MPhil study. The observation spanned in total for ~ 1 hour, with ~ 25 minutes on the target source, IRC+10420. The observation was done at Q-band in which the rest frequency of our target emission line, ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$), is 43.423853 GHz. The array was in configuration D which has the lowest spatial (angular) resolution. This resolution is comparable to that used in previous observation of IRC+10420 for another emission line, ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001), allowing us to compare both emission lines quantitatively as we will explain in later sections. As the phase fluctuation of the radio signal received by the antennae is primarily due to the time variation of atmospheric water vapour, which is particularly rapidly fluctuating at high frequencies like the Q-band (Butler, 1999), we need to adopt a technique known as fast switching observing mode to trace the

atmospheric phase change in a short-enough time scale. The observing mode was carried out by observing IRC+10420 and a nearby secondary (phase) calibrator J1924+1540 (ICRF J192439.4+154043, 4.36° apart) alternately in 5-minute cycles, with ~ 160 s on IRC+10420 and ~ 100 s on J1924+1540. Another quasar J1642+3948 (hereafter 3C345) was observed at the beginning of the observation as the bandpass calibrator.

Unfortunately, none of the standard primary (absolute flux) calibrators was observed. VLA has accurate source models of four calibrators, 3C48, 3C138, 3C147, and 3C286 for Q-band. A source model is important to derive accurate absolute flux scale because when the calibrator is resolved by VLA, especially at high frequency like the Q-band which has high resolution and comparatively weaker flux, the visibility will vary across different baselines and a single flux scale value will be inappropriate for accurate absolute flux calibration. A standard absolute flux calibrator J0137+3309 (3C48) was scheduled to be observed for 10 minutes at the end of our observation. The VLA observing logs suggest that the possible reason for the absence of absolute calibrator could be due to the dynamical scheduling which terminated our observation to perform a ~ 9 -hour testing on WIDAR (a newly-implemented spectral line correlator in VLA) before our scheduled 10-minute scan for 3C48 was performed. We therefore searched for other observations with the same bandpass calibrator as our observation, 3C345, at Q-band and also under D-configuration which are accompanied by a standard absolute flux calibrator for dates close to our observation on IRC+10420. However, there is no source model for 3C345 and we have to assume it to be a point source when carrying out the absolute flux bootstrapping. As summarized in Table 3.1, both observations were taken within 9 days from our IRC+10420 observation. We therefore interpolated the flux of the strong bandpass calibrator (3C345), linearly in time, to perform absolute flux calibration without standard primary (absolute flux) calibrator(s).

As summarized in Table 3.1, there were in total 4 observations with 3C345, including our IRC+10420 observation (denoted as Observation 2), around April 2010. Observation 3 has poor data quality and therefore the entire dataset was discarded. Data reduction was carried out for Observations 1 & 4 to determine the absolute fluxes of 3C345 at the time of observations. The fluxes obtained are 6.07 Jy and 8.355 Jy respectively. The fluxes are then linearly interpolated to estimate the flux of 3C345 during the IRC+10420 observation (Observation 2). The data reduction schemes for observations 1 & 4, and that for IRC+10420 (Observation 2), are the same and will be described below. For Observations 1 & 4, the standard VLA absolute flux calibrator, J1331+3030 (hereafter 3C286), has been observed. Flux density scales of these two observations are all referenced to 3C286. Flux monitoring on 3C286 shows that its flux density appears to remain stable ($\sim 2\%$) over the past few decades in all frequency bands (NRAO, 2011b). At the time of observation and data reduction, the switched power table (SY table) containing information of system gain variations was not freely available on the archival data. Without SY table, the uncertainty of flux bootstrapping for VLA is roughly 10% (NRAO, 2012).

The Q-band flux of 3C345 shown in Table 3.1 is found to have increased by 38% in just 16 days, on average of ~ 0.14 Jy/day. Historically, 3C345 has been found to undergo periodic major flaring events in radio wavelengths every 8 to 10 years (Klare et al., 2005). Larionov et al. (2009) and Schinzel et al. (2012) have shown that 3C345 was undergoing a flaring period starting from 2008 until, at least, mid-2010. Results from VLBA monitoring of 3C345, as shown in Table 3.2, also confirm that its flux at Q-band was varying rapidly around April 2010. Schinzel et al. (2012) attributed this variation to the newly identified “moving emission features” in the radio-emitting jet of 3C345 – which is known to be an active galactic nuclei (AGN) ejecting relativistically moving plasma condensations which produce synchrotron emissions at various wavelengths, including the radio Q-band (43 GHz, 7mm) (Schinzel, 2011).

In addition, rapid variation at the rate 0.14 Jy/day or even higher has been seen towards 3C345 (for example, during May and June 2009, see Table 1 in Schinzel et al., 2012). It should be pointed out that the VLBA flux of 3C345 appeared to be decreasing from April to May 2010 while the VLA flux appeared to be increasing in a shorter timescale in April 2010. Although VLBA and VLA probe emission regions of different scales, the opposite trends of variation means that we have to be cautious about the accuracy of the flux interpolation of 3C345 as observed by VLA at Q-band in April 2010. In addition, we have assumed for simplicity that the Q-band flux of 3C345 as received by VLA varied linearly with time. If we only consider the uncertainty due to absolute flux bootstrapping for those observations with an absolute flux calibrator, which is 10% for Q-band (NRAO, 2012), and assume that the flux of 3C345 near the observation of IRC+10420 on 19 April 2010 was increasing linearly, then the interpolated value of 7.38 Jy has an uncertainty of 10%.

#	Date	Project	Scientific Object(s)	Q-band Flux (7mm) of 3C345 (VLA)
1	10 April 2010	S2053	among other quasars	6.0672 ± 0.0004 Jy
2	19 April 2010	AD621	IRC+10420	7.38 Jy (interpolated)
3	22 April 2010	AD621	AFGL2343	—
4	26 April 2010	AD621	AFGL2343	8.355 ± 0.001 Jy

Table 3.1: VLA D-array observations on 3C345 in Q-band near 19 April 2010.

Date	Q-band Flux (7mm) of 3C345 (VLBA)
6 March 2010	5.470 ± 0.005 Jy
6 April 2010	6.180 ± 0.005 Jy
14 April 2010	5.836 ± 0.004 Jy
19 May 2010	5.049 ± 0.004 Jy
14 June 2010	5.077 ± 0.004 Jy

Table 3.2: Total Q-band (7mm) flux of 3C345 under a VLBA Blazar Monitoring Project (Jorstad, 2010).

3.2 Data Reduction

Data reduction was carried out using the NRAO Astronomical Image Processing System, *AIPS* package (version 31DEC11). The data reduction scheme is based on Section E of the *AIPS Cookbook* (NRAO, 2011a) and is outlined as follows.

First of all, atmospheric opacity, gain curve and antenna position corrections were applied. The (default) seasonal atmospheric opacity model derived by Marvil (2010) was used to estimate the zenith atmospheric opacity at 43 GHz (Q-band). Gain-elevation curve was also corrected under the default manner to eliminate any changes in amplitude due to gravity-induced deformation of the collecting surfaces of the antennae. The correct positions of (E)VLA antennae are obtained from the NRAO baseline correction archive (NRAO, 2010).

The next step is the correction of delay errors. Although the WIDAR correlators of VLA are supposed to correct the geometrical and instrumental

delays across the bandpass (Carlson, 2000), not all the delays of (expanded) VLA had been accurately set by the time of observation (NRAO, 2011a). The residual phase errors will result in a slope of phase across the bandpass (i.e. as a function of frequency). Such errors, known as delay stepping, delay “clunking”, or “fractional bit-shift error”, in our data were found to be of the order 10^{-10} to 10^{-9} seconds, consistent with the reported values (Perley, 2007; Moellenbrock, 2011). In order to restore correlation across the entire bandwidth, delay corrections were derived from the bandpass slope. Fitting was done on the (strongest) bandpass calibrator 3C345 and solution interval of 1 minute was used so as to obtain enough signal-to-noise and avoid loss of coherence due to real phase variation that should be corrected in later gain calibration (Cotton, 1995).

Data were inspected and edited in the standard manner, meaning that all problematic baselines and unreasonably outlying data were flagged and not included in later data reduction process. Bandpass calibration was performed iteratively. In order to derive an accurate bandpass solution (amplitude and phase with respect to frequency), a good amplitude and phase stability with time is desired. On the other hand, an accurate bandpass is required to accurately calibrate the amplitude and phase fluctuation with respect to time (i.e. to perform gain calibration). Therefore we adopted an iterative approach to solve for both bandpass and gain solutions for the bandpass calibrator. We solved for the phase variation with time with solution interval of every sampling so as to correct for the rapid phase fluctuation due to primarily the atmospheric turbulence. Then, after applying the phase calibration, we derived the phase-only bandpass solution and applied the preliminary bandpass solution to the bandpass calibrator. Next, we derived both amplitude and phase solution as a function of time of interval about 1.5 minutes. Another bandpass solution in both amplitude and phase was then derived and also applied to the bandpass calibrator. The iteration of bandpass and gain calibration repeats one more time with both amplitude and phase with the scan length so as to maximize

the signal-to-noise ratio for the final bandpass solution and it is then applied to the secondary calibrator and our target IRC+10420. Absolute flux scale was referenced to the interpolated value for 3C345 (as described in Table 3.1). Gain calibration solutions, for both amplitude and phase, were then derived from the secondary calibrator and applied through linear interpolation to the target source, IRC+10420, to complete the calibration. Finally, both calibrators were imaged to examine the quality of calibration and no artefacts was found.

The interferometric maps were CLEANed, in which the DIRTY beam was deconvolved from the DIRTY maps, under the standard manner with AIPS package (Clark, 1980). In order to enhance signal-to-noise ratio, each channel map presented in this thesis is the average over the velocity range of 4.8416 km s^{-1} . ROBUST weighting was used as a compromise between the needs for small synthesized beam and low RMS noise level. The maps in this thesis adopt `ROBUST = 0` in which the full-width-half-maximum (FWHM) of the synthesized beam is found to be $1''.78 \times 1''.36$ with a position angle (PA) of -44.51° . The RMS noise, estimated from the DIRTY maps of the sourceless channels, is $\sim 5.9 \text{ mJy}$, corresponding to $\sim 1.1 \text{ K}$. For 7 mm, the conversion factor is calculated to be 185.63 K/Jy . Emission from IRC+10420 at velocity channels away from ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line was checked by averaging together all the line-free channels and no continuum emission above $1-\sigma$ level, 1.61 mJy ($= 0.298 \text{ K}$), was detected. By defining the channel that gives the largest emission region as the central channel, the local standard of rest velocity (V_{LSR}) of IRC+10420 was found to be $+73.8897 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, consistent with most other results in the literature as described in Chapter 1. The central channel is also approximately in the middle of the spectral channels with detectable emission.

Previously published (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001) PdBI interferometric maps of IRC+10420's ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) thermal emission were kindly

provided by A. Castro-Carrizo, allowing us to calculate the line ratio of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emissions, defined as ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$). In order to get an accurate estimate of the line ratio, the velocity spacing and spatial resolution of the channel maps for both transitions have to be the same. The PdBI images were regridded into the same velocity spacing (4.8416 km s^{-1}) as our VLA images of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$). Also, our ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) maps have been convolved with the (larger) PdBI synthesized beam ($2''.53 \times 1''.38$, $\text{PA} = 25.98^\circ$) after the CLEAN process.

Chapter 4

Results

Figure 4.1 shows the channel maps in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) at full angular resolution attained in our VLA observation (i.e. synthesized beam of $\text{FWHM} = 1''.78 \times 1''.36$ and $\text{PA} = -44.51^\circ$). Figure 4.2 and 4.3 show the channel maps in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) (the same VLA observation) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (PdBI observation) respectively, both convolved to the same angular resolution (i.e. the larger synthesized beam of $\text{FWHM} = 2''.53 \times 1''.38$ and $\text{PA} = 25.98^\circ$) as in PdBI observation presented in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001). With the identical synthesized beam, we can derive the correct line ratio for analysis as we will describe later.

The full angular resolution channel maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) shown in Figure 4.1 clearly show spatially extended ^{28}SiO thermal emission over an angular radius (centered at the star) of $\sim 4''$. With our adopted distance of IRC+10420 from us of 5 kpc, this angular radius corresponds to a spatial scale of $\sim 20000 \text{ AU} = 3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$. The regions of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission in most channel maps are globally circularly symmetric, although local clumpiness is also seen in the emission. The angular size of the emission region in general decreases away from the systemic velocity ($\sim 74 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) of IRC+10420. This is consistent with a globally spherically expanding envelope

Figure 4.1: VLA maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) thermal emission from IRC+10420. LSR Velocities are indicated in each channel map. Each contour level is $3\sigma = 17.7$ mJy. The greyscale wedge represents the SiO intensity in mJy. The FWHM of the synthesized beam ($1''.78 \times 1''.36$, $\text{PA} = -44.51^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-left corner of the first channel map. North is up and east is left. The cross represents the position of IRC+10420, estimated from 1.3 mm continuum emission (Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009).

Figure 4.2: VLA maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) thermal emission from IRC+10420 convolved with the PdBI synthesized beam from Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001). Each contour level is 3×5.9 mJy.

Figure 4.3: Regrided PdBI maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) thermal emission from IRC+10420, originally published in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) into the same channel spacing as in Figure 4.2 (4.8416 km s^{-1}). LSR Velocities are indicated in each channel map. Each contour level is 80 mJy. The greyscale wedge represents the SiO intensity in mJy. The FWHM of the synthesized beam ($2''.53 \times 1''.38$, $\text{PA} = 25.98^\circ$) is drawn at the bottom-left corner of the first channel map. North is up and east is left. The cross represents the position of IRC+10420, estimated from 1.3 mm continuum emission (Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009). Thanks to Castro-Carrizo A. for kindly providing the fully reduced maps.

with clumpy substructures on smaller scales. For such an envelope, the emission region has the largest angular extent at the systemic velocity (i.e. zero velocity with respect to the star) because the image is just the plane of the sky across the central star. As the velocity channel is further away from the systemic, the image shows the emission region with larger radial velocity (relative to the star) towards or away from us, which occupies a smaller projected area in the plane of the sky. At the most extreme velocity (i.e. the envelope expansion velocity), the emission region should be a circular dot coincide with the stellar position, corresponding to the nearest and farthest point of the envelope from us.

Local clumps can have a significant effect on the intensity of emission. For example, the strongest intensity component, instead of located at the stellar position at the systemic velocity channel, comes from the velocity channel of 53.6 km s^{-1} (i.e. a blueshifted velocity of around 20.3 km s^{-1}). This provides evidence that the distribution of ^{28}SiO -emitting materials in the circumstellar envelope is not perfectly spherically symmetric. It is also evident, in particular for the central channels from 64.0 km s^{-1} to 89.9 km s^{-1} , that there is an enhancement of emission along a ring-like structure at a radius of around $2''$, about 10000 AU. Similar to ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission, the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission from the envelope of IRC+10420 also shows similar ring-like enhancement, but at an inner radius of around $1''.5$ (~ 7500 AU). Beyond the ring, there is extended emission up to approximately $\sim 4''$ (~ 20000 AU). The envelope exhibits centrally depressed emission, compared to the enhanced ring of emission, for both transitions. The enhanced ring of emission with central depression is also seen in ^{12}CO emission as imaged by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) as we have mentioned in Section 2.3. However, the extended enhancement in emission is particularly unusual for ^{28}SiO . As we have mentioned in Section 2.4, the gas-phase SiO molecules should have been depleted onto silicate dust grains at a radius of at most $\lesssim 10^{16} \text{ cm}$ (~ 1000 AU) from the central star. This corresponds to an angular size of less

than $0''.2$ for the case of IRC+10420 (assuming a distance of 5 kpc). The expected ^{28}SiO -emitting region should therefore be a compact concentration at the stellar position, and at most barely resolved, if not unresolved.

Closer examination on the channel maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) reveals a slight shift of the position of peak emission across the velocity channels. The position of the peak of emission is slightly away from IRC+10420, towards the southwest at velocities more blueshifted than $\lesssim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$; while it is seen towards the north-east from IRC+10420 at velocities more redshifted than $\gtrsim 105 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In order to examine the kinematics of the envelope, we have plotted the position-velocity (PV) diagram. Figure 4.4 shows the PV diagram along the position angle of 70° (angle measured from North to East). This PV diagram with an angular resolution of $1''.78 \times 1''.36$ shows a velocity gradient of $(52.0 \pm 2.4) \text{ km s}^{-1} / (1''.42 \pm 0''.78) \approx (36.6 \pm 20.1) \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$, increasing from southwest to northeast. The uncertainties are half of the synthesized beam and half of the velocity separation between channel maps, and are propagated in quadrature. This is only qualitatively consistent with previous findings of $(50.2 \pm 2.5) \text{ km s}^{-1} / (0.788 \pm 0''.79) \approx (63.7 \pm 56.6) \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$ (as indicated in straight line across the pattern) for ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission under an angular resolution of $1''.5 \times 1''.3$ (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007). A smaller of velocity gradient in the unit of $\text{km s}^{-1} \text{ arcsec}^{-1}$ indicates a larger shift of emission peak (in arcsec) across spectral channels (in km s^{-1}). Although the direction of velocity gradient is the same, the values estimated from the relative shift of the emission peaks are different. The velocity gradient observed from ^{28}SiO emissions should be interpreted with caution because of the clumpy and non-spherical nature of the envelope surrounding the central star. For example, as we can see in Figures 4.4, the emission peak between $\sim 90 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and 100 km s^{-1} is located towards the southwest of the star, same direction as the blueshifted velocity ($\lesssim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). We are unable to observe a global velocity gradient as in ^{12}CO presumably because of the more clumpy distribution of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions.

On the other hand, as shown in Figure 4.5, the velocity gradient is not obvious for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission for which the estimated value is $> 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}\text{arcsec}^{-1}$ (i.e. the shift in emission peak across velocity channels is less than $0.05 \text{ (arcsec)}/(\text{kms}^{-1})$). In order to check if the absence of velocity gradient in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) is due to the size of synthesized beam, we convolved our VLA image for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) into the larger synthesized beam with the size of $2''.53 \times 1''.38$ and $\text{PA} = 25.98^\circ$ as in PdBI observation for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). Figure 4.6 shows the PV diagram of convolved ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) channel maps and the emission still exhibits, apparently, a slight velocity gradient of $(53.2 \pm 2.4) \text{ km s}^{-1}/(0''.77 \pm 0''.93) \approx (69.2 \pm 84.1) \text{ km s}^{-1}\text{arcsec}^{-1}$. The uncertainties is dominated by the half size of the PdBI synthesized beam. Thus the difference in angular resolution between the VLA and PdBI observations does not fully explain the absence of velocity gradient in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$).

Apart from ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$), Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) also found a similar velocity gradient for SO ($J_K = 6_5-5_4$). Although it is possible that the velocity gradient is a mere observational coincidence due to the clumpiness of the envelope and random positions of dense clumps with strong emission, the fact that we observe a qualitatively consistent, small velocity gradient across various molecular lines, and among different transitions, indicates the gradient is more likely to be true. If so, then the SiO thermal emission region around IRC+10420 is indeed kinematically connected to the circumstellar envelope as traced in ^{12}CO . We speculate the reason for the absence of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) velocity gradient to be the clumpiness of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions in the circumstellar environment around IRC+10420. The clumps that preferably emit ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) could be distributed more similarly to the bulk, ^{12}CO -emitting envelope than those clumps that preferably emit ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$).

In order to calculate the ratio of the line brightness temperature, both

Figure 4.4: Position-velocity (PV) diagram of the VLA observation on ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) along $\text{PA} = 70^\circ$. Horizontal axis represents the LSR Velocities in km s^{-1} ; vertical axis represents the relative offset, from south-west ($0''$) to north-east ($15''$) along the 70° -axis. Note that this relative offset axis is opposite to Figure 2.9 as published by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007). Greyscale represents the intensity of emission in the unit of milli-Jansky. Position and systemic velocity of IRC+10420 ($\text{RA} = 19^{\text{h}}26^{\text{m}}48^{\text{s}}.09$, $V_{\text{LSR}} = 73.8897 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) are indicated by the horizontal and vertical reference lines respectively. The velocity gradient of ^{12}CO envelope observed by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) as estimated from Figure 2.9 was indicated by the straight line across the pattern.

Figure 4.5: Position-velocity (PV) diagram of the PdBI observation on ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) along $\text{PA} = 70^\circ$ (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). Captions are same as Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.6: Position-velocity (PV) diagram of the VLA observation on ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$), convolved to the larger PdBI beam ($2''.53 \times 1''.38$, $\text{PA} = 25.98^\circ$), along $\text{PA} = 70^\circ$. Captions are same as Figure 4.4.

maps were convolved with the same PdBI synthesized beam and regridded into the same set of velocities. The spatial and spectral resolutions of our VLA observation in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission are therefore downgraded.

The RMS noise level of the PdBI observation in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) was not provided in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)’s paper. Theoretical estimation from Equation (1) in Winters & Neri (2011) gives the RMS per synthesized beam of $\gtrsim 35$ mJy (using $T_{\text{sys}} = 150$ K and on-source integration time per configuration of 5130 seconds, Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001), while the (CLEANed) channel maps near the end channels (i.e. near the extreme velocities) in Figure 4.3 consistently give a RMS noise of ~ 5 mJy. Although the end channels are not completely line-free, the emission from the envelope is very weak and therefore we do not expect much effect on the RMS noise due to the CLEAN (beam deconvolution) process. We adopted the value of 5 mJy as the RMS noise for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) intensity as it is the observed value obtained from the channel maps.

The azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profiles for both ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) transition lines, at the channel nearest to the systemic velocity, are plotted in Figure 4.7. Due to limitation of the size of synthesized beam ($2''.53 \times 1''.38$), the profiles were sampled, for the sake of signal-to-noise ratio, in radial intervals of $0''.70$, corresponding to 5.25×10^{16} cm assuming the distance of 5 kpc from us. Both lines exhibit an apparent central depression for radius smaller than $\sim 2''$ from IRC+10420, while the depression for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) seems to be “deeper” than ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). Also, the brightness temperature profile of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) seems to peak at an inner radius ($\sim 1''$) than that of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) ($\sim 2''$). The shift in the peak intensities is not obvious in the channel maps because of the clumpiness of the envelope. The intensity of emissions from both lines decline beyond $\sim 2''$. The emissions seem to fall at a larger gradient within $\sim 2'' - 4''$ than beyond $4''$, possibly suggesting

the mass-loss rate and/or physical conditions in these two radial ranges of the envelope may be different. Beam convolution effect cannot explain the difference because the FWHM of the synthesized beam is only $\sim 1''.87$, less than the scale of the change in brightness temperature profiles.

Apart from the two available radial brightness temperature profiles, we also computed for the first time the radial profile of the line brightness temperature ratio in ^{28}SiO , which is defined as $^{28}\text{SiO}(2-1)/^{28}\text{SiO}(1-0)$. Figure 4.8 shows the radial line ratio profile. The line ratio near the central star is the highest, at value of roughly 2.2. As we will explain later, a high line ratio indicates that the emission is in optically thin regime. At around the radius of peak emission between $\sim 1''.5$ and $\sim 2''$, the line ratio is roughly between 1.2 and 1.5. Beyond $\sim 2''$, the line ratio decreases to ~ 1 , indicating an optically thick regime. The optical thickness indicates the number of e -foldings of intensity reduction as the radiation travel along the line-of-sight through the envelope.

The line ratio calculation is subject to two major uncertainties which may affect the absolute values of the ratio, although the overall trend, decreasing from the centre to around $2''$ and remains roughly constant outwards, is likely to be true. First, as discussed previously in Chapter 3, no standard absolute flux calibrator was present at the time of our VLA observation. Without an accurate flux calibration for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$), the uncertainty of the intensity profile may be much larger than what we expect from the RMS noise. Even with an absolute flux calibrator, the systematic uncertainty of absolute flux calibration for VLA at Q-band is roughly 10% (NRAO, 2012). The RMS noise from our VLA observation is of order $\gtrsim 7\%$ near the peak emission and the fraction is larger at other radii. Therefore the uncertainty of absolute flux calibration contributes significantly to the source of error in our derivation of the radial brightness temperature profile for the region with high intensity. The RMS noise will dominate over the uncertainty in absolute flux towards

Figure 4.7: Azimuthally averaged radial brightness temperature profiles for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). Conversion factor and map noise of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) are 185.63 K/Jy, 1.1 K/beam = 5.9 mJy/beam, and those of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) are 46.47 K/Jy, 0.26 K/beam = 5.5 mJy/beam respectively. Uncertainty bars have been scaled as the inverse square root of the annular ring coverage (in unit of synthesized beams).

Figure 4.8: Line brightness temperature ratio of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) over ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) computed from the intensity profile as shown in Figure 4.7. Uncertainty bars have been calculated in standard manner of error propagation.

the outskirts of the envelope.

In addition to the absolute flux problem, the amount of diffuse emission from the envelope of IRC+10420 may contribute to the uncertainty in flux measurement and hence the line ratio calculation. However, we will explain below that the effect is unlikely to significantly affect our results. Figure 4.9 plots the real part visibilities of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$), averaged over the channels with ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission from IRC+10420. There was no zero-spacing data on ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) for IRC+10420 and the shortest baseline in our VLA observation has a uv -distance of ~ 44.0 metres, which is blind to emissions of scale $\gtrsim 32''$ (i.e. λ/D). From the channel maps shown in Figure 4.1, we noticed that the spatial extent of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$)-emitting region is roughly $4''$, similar to that detected in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) using PdBI (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). For comparison, the shortest baseline in the previous PdBI observation by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) is ~ 32.0 metres, corresponding to a largest detectable scale of $\lesssim 23''$ (Winters & Neri, 2011). The spatial extent of IRC+10420's envelope, after combining interferometric and single-dish data, is found to be up to roughly $10''$ as traced in ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$), and up to roughly $8''$ in ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) (Figures 2 and 3 in Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007). The maximum detectable extent of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s observation, which combined the IRAM 30 m single dish and PdBI interferometer data, is about $80''$. Using the formula derived by Wilner & Welch (1994) (their Equation A7), and assuming that the extent of ^{28}SiO -emitting envelope is at most of the same order as ^{12}CO , i.e. $\lesssim 10''$, we found that our VLA configuration for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) can recover 71% of the ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) flux from an emission scale of FWHM = $10''$ (the scale of ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) emission), and the PdBI configuration adopted by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) observation can recover 49% of the flux from the same scale of extended emission. If we assume the FWHM of the ^{28}SiO emission scale to be $8''$ (i.e. the scale of ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emission), then VLA observation can recover 80% of the flux for

^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and PdBI observation can recover 63% of the flux for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). No single dish observations on ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line has ever been done so far and therefore the flux of diffuse emission cannot be completely recovered. However, since ^{28}SiO molecules have higher critical densities than ^{12}CO , they require significantly higher gas density than ^{12}CO in order to produce strong emission as we and Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) have detected. Therefore, the ^{28}SiO -emitting region should not be more spatially extended than the envelope traced in ^{12}CO . As a result, the actual size of ^{28}SiO emission is likely to be at most $8''$, if not much less than that. This means most of the corresponding flux from ^{28}SiO emission should be recovered by the baseline coverage of our current VLA observation and the previous PdBI observation. So we may assume the accuracy of flux measurement is not severely affected by the missing flux problem.

The error bars shown in Figures 4.7 and 4.8 only represent the RMS noise obtained from the channel maps, regardless of the uncertainties in absolute flux calibration of other observations, flux interpolation due to missing primary (absolute flux) calibrator, and any missing flux due to extended emission.

Figure 4.9: IRC+10420 ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) real part visibilities (in mJy) plotted against uv -distance (in $k\lambda$, ~ 6.9 m) from VLA observation. The smallest uv -spacing in the dataset is $6375\lambda \approx 44.0$ m.

Chapter 5

Modelling the ^{28}SiO Emission

We have imaged, for the first time, the ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission. By combining with Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) image, we can then measure the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line ratio and study how this ratio changes with radius. The line brightness temperature ratio provides us an intuitive way to model the physical conditions such as molecular hydrogen gas density and ^{28}SiO molecular abundance of the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420.

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found that the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission peaks in brightness temperature at a radius of about $1''$, as shown in Figure 4.7. As we also show in the same figure, however, the brightness temperature in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) peaks further out at a radius of about $2''$. Both transitions therefore exhibit a central depression in ^{28}SiO . Furthermore, in both transitions, the ^{28}SiO emission can be detected out to a radius of about $6''$. As shown in Figure 4.8, the line ratio in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) decreases from near 2.0 at a radius less than $1''$ from the star to ~ 1.2 at about $2''$, and remains roughly constant at a value close to ~ 1.0 beyond this radius. If, as we show, the density is high enough that ^{28}SiO is thermalized, the relatively high line ratio seen towards the inner

regions indicates that the ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) lines are close to optically thin, whereas line ratio values close to unity in the outer part of the envelope suggests that the lines there are optically thick.

This chapter describe our effort to model both brightness temperature profiles and the line ratio profile as a function of radius from IRC+10420. The line ratio gives a instructive estimate to infer the gas density, kinetic temperature and optical depth of the emission. Given the optical depth and brightness temperature, one can infer the ^{28}SiO column density and therefore, for a given thickness through the envelope, the molecular abundance.

To excite ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) transitions as observed, the molecular gas density must be comparable to their critical densities, which are $6 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respectively (Schöier et al., 2005). Modelling of the ^{12}CO envelope by both Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) suggest a density profile of order 10^4 cm^{-3} close to the centre and 10^3 cm^{-3} in the outer envelope to explain the ^{12}CO emission. As we show below in Section 5.3, these values of gas density much less than 10^5 cm^{-3} are likely insufficient to produce the strong ^{28}SiO emission similar to that observed, unless either of the following assumptions has been made: (1) the gas kinetic temperature is elevated to an unreasonably high value of more than 700 K; or (2) the ^{28}SiO column density is strongly enhanced. As we will show, however, in Section 5.3 that the later assumption leads to optically thick emission and cannot explain the high line ratio of about 2 towards the central star.

The inadequacy of the current density profile as inferred from ^{12}CO emission to simultaneously explain emission from both ^{28}SiO transitions motivates us to derive a different model for the physical conditions of ^{28}SiO -emitting region. With our new VLA interferometric observation in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$), our model for the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions is constrained by the radial

profiles of the brightness temperatures for the two lowest ^{28}SiO rotational transitions. In addition to these, the measurement of the line ratio as defined by $^{28}\text{SiO} (J = 2-1, v = 0)/^{28}\text{SiO} (J = 1-0, v = 0)$ provides a more instructive way to infer the physical conditions.

The major parameters describing the physical conditions of the molecular emission are gas kinetic temperature, molecular gas density and ^{28}SiO relative abundance (which alters the ^{28}SiO column density). We treat the density and abundance as free parameters in our radiative transfer model as will be described in Section 5.2, while adopt a derived profile of temperature from available ^{12}CO model for reasons discussed in Section 5.2.

For a given gas kinetic temperature, an increase in column density of ^{28}SiO along the line of sight leads to an increase in the emission intensity. Therefore, it is clear that the modelled brightness temperature increases with input gas density and/or ^{28}SiO abundance (i.e. the ^{28}SiO column density). On the other hand, the interplay between gas density and ^{28}SiO column density on the line ratio is not trivial. As we will explore the more specific ranges of parameters with simple LVG calculations with the code **RADEX** (van der Tak et al., 2007), the line ratio varies in a complicated manner as a function of density and column density/abundance.

In this chapter, we will first explore the physical ranges of gas density and ^{28}SiO abundance/column density using the LVG code **RADEX** and explain the underlying physics in Section 5.1. Then, we will explain our radiative transfer code for the modelling of the ^{28}SiO emission in Section 5.2. As one of the input assumption, our choice of the adopted kinetic temperature profile which we think best-fit the ^{12}CO envelope will be discussed in Section 5.2. The ^{28}SiO emission will be modelled with our radiative transfer code in Section 5.3. We first test if Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s model for $^{28}\text{SiO} (J = 2-1, v = 0)$ emission explains the $^{28}\text{SiO} (J = 1-0, v = 0)$ emission and the line ratio

between the two transitions. As we will show, the physical conditions (density, abundance and temperature) as applied to their model cannot explain fully our ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) observation and hence the line ratio. Then we propose our physical model, based on the plausible ranges of parameters as suggested by RADEX calculations to better explain the observed ^{28}SiO emission.

5.1 Dependence of Line Ratio on Density and Abundance

To obtain a preliminary understanding of how the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line ratio varies with gas density, kinetic temperature and ^{28}SiO relative abundance through the envelope of IRC+10420, we make use of the fast radiative transfer code RADEX (van der Tak et al., 2007). RADEX adopts the large velocity gradient (LVG, or Sobolev) approximation (Sobolev, 1960) in which radiative transfer is treated as a local problem and the photon will not be absorbed by molecules in the neighbouring envelope along the line of sight due to large Doppler shift caused by the velocity change (as compared to the thermal line width) (Kwok, 2007). Although this approximation is not valid for the envelope of IRC+10420 because we expect the turbulence velocity is relatively large ($\sim 3 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) compared to other AGB stars (e.g. ?), LVG approach serves as a quick guide for us to qualitatively understand how different parameters affect the line ratio.

This program solves the system of statistical equilibrium equations, which relates the (1) spontaneous de-excitation, (2) radiative excitation and de-excitation, and (3) collisional excitation and de-excitation processes between upper and lower (rotational transition) levels by escape probability method (Sobolev, 1960; Castor, 1970) in order to decouple the level populations from the “average radiation field intensity”. The average radiation field intensity

is expressed in terms of escape probability $\beta(\tau)$ which enables the system of statistical equilibrium equations to be solved iteratively. For LVG approximation, we select $\beta_{\text{LVG}}(\tau) = (1 - e^{-\tau})/\tau$ (e.g. Elitzur, 1992) in the RADEX code, where τ is the optical depth.

RADEX calculation of the brightness temperature and hence line ratio requires temperature, density and ^{28}SiO column density (N_{SiO} , cm^{-2}) as the input parameters. For a given radial depth r_d through the envelope, the ^{28}SiO abundance is related to the column density by the relationship $N_{\text{SiO}} = n_{\text{H}_2} \times ([\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2]) \times r_d$. We use LVG approximation here by assuming the physical system as an expanding spherical envelope with an increasing velocity with radius. Also, we adopt a constant kinetic temperature (T_{kin}) and a constant gas density (n_{H_2}) throughout each model envelope. Figure 5.1 shows the RADEX calculations of the line ratio (colour scale) for a given combination of molecular gas density (n_{H_2} , cm^3) (vertical axis) and ^{28}SiO column density (N_{SiO}) (horizontal axis) at different kinetic temperatures (shown in different panels). We include a set of kinetic temperatures, ranging from 20 K (corresponding to the outermost radius) to 1000 K (corresponding to the innermost radius). We also span a wide range of possible gas densities from 10^3 to 10^8 cm^{-3} and column densities from 10^{13} to $\sim 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Figure 5.2 shows the RADEX calculations of the line ratio (colour scale) for a given combination of molecular gas density (n_{H_2} , cm^3) (vertical axis) and ^{28}SiO relative abundance ($[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2]$) (horizontal axis) at selected kinetic temperatures, representing high and low temperatures, and at various outer radii ($0''.5$, $1''.0$ and $2''.0$) of the model envelope. As we will show, these radii are representative of the thickness of regions with different line ratios.

From the plots displayed in Figures 5.1 and 5.2, we observe the following trends of line ratio (in brightness temperature) and the physics can be understood as follows. First, at a given gas density and relative ^{28}SiO abundance, the line ratio only changes slightly, if not remains essentially the same, over

the range of kinetic temperature shown. The excitation energies of both the ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) transitions correspond to kinetic temperatures of less than 10 K, meaning that the emissions from the low transitions of ^{28}SiO molecules do not contribute much to the cooling of the gas envelope (e.g. González Delgado et al., 2003). Therefore, as long as the gas kinetic temperature exceeds 10 K, the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line ratio is insensitive to the change in kinetic temperature. Second, at a given ^{28}SiO column density or, equivalently, relative ^{28}SiO abundance for a given depth through the envelope, the line ratio generally increases with increasing molecular density. Considering all the panels in Figures 5.1 and 5.2 as a whole, high line ratio with a maximum value of 4.0 is found on the top-left part of both figures, corresponding to high gas density and low column density or, equivalently, ^{28}SiO relative abundance regime. By comparison, a low line ratio which tends to values < 1.0 is found at the bottom parts of the figures, corresponding to low gas density and low abundance regime. We will now explain the physical reasons why different line ratios are found at different combinations of densities and ^{28}SiO column densities/abundances.

As calculated from parameters in the LAMDA database (Schöier et al., 2005), the critical density ($n_c = A_{ul}/C_{ul}$) for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) is approximately $6 \times 10^4 = 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) is approximately $3 \times 10^5 = 10^{5.3} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. At high density limit where $n_{\text{H}_2}(r) \gg 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, both transition lines are excited and de-excited predominantly by collisions and the level populations will follow Boltzmann distribution. Therefore, in the (1) optically thin regime (optical depth $\tau \ll 1$) where the column density is low (less than 10^{15} cm^{-2} at $T \gtrsim 100 \text{ K}$), and (2) local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE), the brightness temperature can be approximated as $T_b = T_{\text{bg}}e^{-\tau} + T_{\text{kin}}(1 - e^{-\tau}) \approx T_{\text{bg}} + T_{\text{kin}}\tau$ (for high temperature envelope, $T_{\text{kin}} \gg T_{\text{bg}}$, such as that of IRC+10420). Hence the line ratio will tend to the ratio of the optical depth τ at the line centre. The optical depth, defined as the integral of the amount of absorption of radiation along the ray from the

source to the observer, $\tau \sim (A_{ul}/\nu^3) \cdot x_u \cdot [1 - \exp(-h\nu/kT_{\text{ex}})]$ is derived from the level populations under statistical equilibrium and LTE at the optically thin limit, where A_{ul} is the Einstein coefficient of the transition between an upper energy state (u) to a lower energy state (l), ν is the frequency of the corresponding transition line and, x_u is the fractional population relative to the density of the u^{th} energy state ($J = 0$ is the 1st state) of a particular molecule. In our case of ^{28}SiO molecules, the line ratio at optically thin limit is calculated to be 4.0. In the case of optically thick regime, on the other hand, the line ratio tends to 1.0 because $T_b = T_{\text{bg}}e^{-\tau} + T_{\text{kin}}(1 - e^{-\tau}) \approx T_{\text{kin}}$. To obtain a line ratio in the range above 1.0 (up to ~ 2.2) as found at radii within $2''.0$ as shown in Figure 4.8, the gas density is required to have a high value of $\sim 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This gas density is 1 – 2 orders of magnitude higher than that of ^{12}CO -emitting envelope in which the density is of order $10^3 - 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (e.g. Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009), suggesting that the ^{28}SiO is produced in localized regions of enhanced gas density immersed in more diffuse gas that produces the bulk of the ^{12}CO emission.

At densities of $n_{\text{H}_2}(r) \ll 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, much lower than the critical densities of at least $\sim 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and if in the situation where the column density and hence ^{28}SiO relative abundance is not too high to make the line optically thick, then ^{28}SiO molecules are spontaneously de-excited (radiatively) to the ground state whenever they get excited. The rate of such de-excitation would simply follow the rate of the (collisional and radiative) excitation, and the emission from lower transitions will be stronger by cascades from higher levels. In this regime, the line ratio will therefore tend to values less than unity.

In the regime where the gas density comparable to the critical value of $\sim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ or above, the line ratio generally decreases with increasing column density and hence relative abundance from the optically thin limit of 4.0 to optically thick limit of about 1.0, corresponding to the right edges of the figures. For an optically thick emission, the intensities of both transitions would

become the blackbody source function of the envelope. This results in a line brightness temperature ratio close to unity.

Finally, there are a number of deep red/blue or discontinuously valued pixels, typically at high column density ($> 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in Figure 5.1) or at high abundance ($> 10^{-5}$ for low temperatures; $> 10^{-7}$ for high temperatures in Figure 5.2). When the optical depth is very high, photons are trapped inside the gaseous envelope and may contribute to stimulated emission of the excited molecules. For a particular transition, radiative trapping of photons emitted from spontaneous downward transitions from even higher levels (which means the density is below critical for those higher transitions) will lead to a higher excitation temperature than the gas kinetic temperature, $T_{\text{ex}} > T_{\text{kin}}$ (Elitzur, 1982). In terms of level populations, the upper level of this transition is more populated than the thermal (Boltzmann) regime and this is known as “suprathemal emission”. When the trapping is strong enough to produce population inversion, in which the upper level is more populated than the lower level (or mathematically, a negative T_{ex} or negative optical depth τ), then maser emission occurs and strong amplification (exponential along the path) of that transition line will follow (Elitzur, 1982; Kwok, 2007). Since extremely high excitation temperature may occur to either one or both transitions, the resulted line ratio may take a wide range of values. This explains qualitatively the presence of deep red/blue and randomly valued pixels in the plots. However, the exact values are meaningless as stated by van der Tak et al. (2007) that the escape probability approximation is not valid for maser emission. White pixels represent the parameters that result in negative fluxes that are unphysical. No explanation was provided by the code regarding these results.

(b) $T_{\text{kin}} = 50 \text{ K}$

(d) $T_{\text{kin}} = 230 \text{ K}$

(f) $T_{\text{kin}} = 1000$ K

Figure 5.1: Simulated line brightness temperature ratio (the colour scale) of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) over ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) as a function of number density of molecular hydrogen gas (vertical axis: n_{H_2} , cm^{-3}) and *column density of SiO molecules along the line of sight* (horizontal axis: N_{SiO} , cm^{-2}), at different gas temperatures (caption: T_{kin} , K). Results are calculated by non-LTE code RADEX (van der Tak et al., 2007) using large velocity gradient (LVG) approximation for escape probability.

(b) $T_{\text{kin}} = 500 \text{ K}, r = 0''.5$

(d) $T_{\text{kin}} = 250 \text{ K}, r = 1''.$

(f) $T_{\text{kin}} = 160 \text{ K}, r = 2''.0$

Figure 5.2: Simulated line brightness temperature ratio (the colour scale) of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1, v = 0$) over ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0, v = 0$) as a function of number density of molecular hydrogen gas (vertical axis: n_{H_2} , cm^{-3}) and *relative abundance of SiO molecules* (horizontal axis: $[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2]$, dimensionless), at different radii and gas temperatures (caption: T_{kin} , K; r , arcsec). Results are calculated in the same manner as Figure 5.1.

5.2 The Radiative Transfer Code

We modelled the envelope of IRC+10420 as traced by ^{28}SiO using the one-dimensional radiative transfer code developed by Dinh-V-Trung & Nguyen-Q-Rieu (2000). This code was previously applied by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) to ^{12}CO emission. Rather than employing the LVG approximation as in RADEX, the code directly solves the coupled system of equations of radiative transfer and statistical equilibrium for the envelope as a whole. We used a grid of 90 radial mesh points to represent the envelope of IRC+10420. The code uses the accelerated Λ -iteration method to speed up the convergence to a solution in the radiative transfer problem. Once the computation of level population converges, we convolved the resultant model brightness temperature distribution with a circular, Gaussian beam having a FWHM of $1''.87$, which is equal to the geometric mean of the major and minor axes of the synthesized beam ($2''.53 \times 1''.38$) in our ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) maps. In this way, the area of the convolving beams in the model and observed maps are the same.

We adopted a local turbulence velocity of 3 km s^{-1} , which is the same as adopted by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) to model the ^{12}CO envelope. A much smaller local turbulence velocity than the expansion velocity is usually adopted under the constraint of the size of the line wings. The typical value adopted for circumstellar envelope around AGB stars is 1 km s^{-1} . The smooth ^{12}CO line profiles as seen from this envelope of large expansion velocity ($> 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) compared to typical AGB stars (typical $V_{\text{exp}} \lesssim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) motivates a larger value for turbulence velocity than the typical. We find that the exact value of the adopted local turbulence velocity does not change the model result significantly. All rotational transition levels of ^{28}SiO up to $J = 20$ in the ground state and first vibrational state were included. Higher vibrational states are ignored because the excitation energies ($> 3500 \text{ K}$, e.g. Su et al., 2012) are

way too high compared to the kinetic temperature in IRC+10420's envelope. We obtained the collisional cross-sections of ^{28}SiO with H_2 from Schöier et al. (2005), who scale up the collisional cross-sections of ^{28}SiO with He from Dayou & Balança (2006) by a factor of 1.38 and interpolate the scaled values. Since the gas density is low in the envelope of IRC+10420, radiative de-excitation dominates over collisional. Therefore, we ignore collisional de-excitation to the vibrational state $v = 0$ in our calculations.

Unlike the case of the envelope around hypergiant AFGL2343 (Quintana-Lacaci et al., 2008) where infrared radiation does not play any significant role in the excitation of ^{28}SiO molecule, in the case of IRC+10420 the infrared emission by hot dust located close to the hypergiant is strong and expected to contribute to the excitation of ^{28}SiO molecule. As mentioned in Section 2.2, the inner envelope of IRC+10420 is optically thick in the optical. Since the optically thick dust shell absorbs stellar radiation in the optical and reradiates in the infrared, we need to be concerned whether the intense infrared radiation from the dust shell plays a significant role in exciting the ^{28}SiO molecules. Infrared photons at $8\mu\text{m}$ from the hot dust shell can excite ^{28}SiO from any rotational level J in the ground vibrational state ($v = 0$) to the levels $J \pm 1$ in the excited vibrational state ($v = 1$). ^{28}SiO then de-excites rapidly through spontaneous radiative transitions to rotational levels $J \pm 2$ in the ground vibrational state. In our model, for simplicity we assume that all the infrared photons at $8\mu\text{m}$ come from an optically thick shell at an arbitrary kinetic temperature $T = 400$ K located close to the hypergiant. The outer radius of this dust shell is then estimated to be 8×10^{15} cm in order to reproduce the amount of $8\mu\text{m}$ flux from IRC+10420 measured in March 1992 by Jones et al. (1993). The size of the dust shell is about a factor of 3 smaller than the inner radius of the ^{28}SiO envelope.

The most important input parameters for modelling the ^{28}SiO emission are the molecular hydrogen (H_2) gas density, gas kinetic temperature, and ^{28}SiO

abundance (relative to H_2) for a given depth through the envelope. The ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0, v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1, v = 0$) transitions have excitation energies corresponding to temperatures well below 10 K (Schöier et al., 2005). By comparison, the envelope as traced in ^{12}CO has kinetic temperatures ranging from $\sim 500 - 1000$ K in the inner envelope (radius of $\sim 0''.5$) to $\sim 30 - 50$ K in the outer envelope (radius of $3'' - 6''$) (e.g. Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009; Teyssier et al., 2012). As a consequence, ^{28}SiO emission in the low transitions do not contribute much to the cooling of the molecular gas (e.g. González Delgado et al., 2003). Therefore the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1, v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0, v = 0$) line ratio is relatively insensitive to the exact value for the kinetic temperature of the envelope, although the individual brightness temperature of the ^{28}SiO emission does depend on the gas kinetic temperature.

As a starting point, we adopt a gas kinetic temperature for the SiO-emitting region to be the same as that inferred for the CO envelope. There are three models, all based in part or exclusively on CO measurements, for how the kinetic temperature of the envelope varies with radius from the central star. Both Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Teyssier et al. (2012) adopt a power law profile for the envelope temperature, but with different temperatures at the innermost region of the envelope. By contrast, Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) derived the temperature profile by calculating the thermal energy balance (between heating and cooling processes) of the ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO molecular gases and successfully fit their high-spatial resolution ^{12}CO maps (for ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$)) and spectra (for all transitions up to ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$)) available at that time. The calculated temperature profile of Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) for the inner envelope ($< 2''.0 = 1.5 \times 10^{17}$ cm) ranges from about 60 to 140 K, which is much lower than those derived by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Teyssier et al. (2012) adopting power-laws, ranging from 150 K to at least ~ 700 K; while for the outer envelope, their kinetic temperature profiles are comparable to each other, of roughly 30 to 60 K. However, as Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) mentioned, the thermal energy

balance calculation does not include possible shock heating which may cause an elevated kinetic temperature.

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) modelled the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope with a high gas kinetic temperature profile, up to about 1200 K at the inner boundary of the ^{12}CO envelope at 2.5×10^{16} cm = $0''.33$. The basis for such a high temperature comes from their modelling on single-dish ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$) spectrum measured by Teyssier et al. (2006). The excitation energy of ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$) corresponds to a temperature of ~ 120 K (Schöier et al., 2005) and therefore the transition better probes the hotter, inner envelope than lower transitions of ^{12}CO . Subsequent to Teyssier et al. (2006), Teyssier et al. (2012) obtained high-spectral resolution ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO spectra for even higher transitions including $J = 6-5$, $J = 10-9$ and $J = 16-15$, as shown in Figure 5.3. Combining with previous spectra for lower CO transitions, Teyssier et al. (2012) model the radial gas kinetic temperature profile with the set of CO spectra covering a wide range of excitation energies. The corresponding temperatures they probe range from less than 10 K to 752 K. As constrained by the intensities of the highest transition, i.e. $J = 16-15$ of both ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO , Teyssier et al. (2012) inferred a lower kinetic temperature (by $\sim 30\%$) for the radial range of the inner ^{12}CO -emitting shell.

As an initial guess of the kinetic temperature of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions, we adopted the power-law temperature model of Teyssier et al. (2012) for radii less than $1''.65 = 1.24 \times 10^{17}$ cm. We believe the temperature of the inner regions to be better constrained by high- J transitions of ^{12}CO , therefore we prefer Teyssier et al. (2012)'s first temperature profile for the inner shell. For regions beyond, we adopt the temperature profile of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s profile because it can be easily expressed analytically and does not differ greatly from the temperature profile as derived by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009).

Specifically, the adopted temperature profile is as follows (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Teyssier et al., 2012):

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{T_{\text{kin}}}{\text{K}}\right)_{\text{inner}}(r) &= 170 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-1.2} & 0.25 \leq \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 1.24 \\ \left(\frac{T_{\text{kin}}}{\text{K}}\right)_{\text{outer}}(r) &= 100 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-0.8} & 1.24 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 5.20 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5.3: Figure 7 of Teyssier et al. (2012) showing the high-spectral resolution ^{12}CO and ^{13}CO spectra of IRC+10420 spanning a wide range of transitions. As the excitation energies of all transitions span from lower than 10 K to higher than 750 K, the radial kinetic temperature profile for IRC+10420's envelope is strongly constrained (under the assumed density profiles and relative CO abundance). The modelled line profiles using the modified kinetic temperature profile for the inner shell (about 30% lower than that adopted by (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007)) are drawn in thick red curves. The value on the top-right corner of each panel indicates the correction factor for absolute calibration errors. Although the modelled line profiles do not fully simulate all the features in the observed profiles (especially for the lower transitions), the model provides very good first order approximations of line intensities for all observed transitions.

5.3 Previous Physical Model of ^{28}SiO -Emitting Regions

There is only one previous attempt to model the ^{28}SiO envelope of IRC+10420 (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) has imaged the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission line and modelled the observed channel maps. They proposed that the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission from the envelope of IRC+10420 as coming from a thin, detached shell with inner radius of 9×10^{16} cm ($1''.20$), and outer radius of 1.4×10^{17} cm ($1''.87$). As we can see from the radial brightness temperature profile from Figure 4.7, this radial range roughly corresponds to the emission peak of the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) transition. Assuming that the ^{28}SiO emission originates from the same gas as that responsible for producing the ^{12}CO emission with an attributed constant mass-loss rate of $3.6 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, the gas density at the inner radius of the abovementioned shell is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 2.15 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and at the outer radius is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 8.88 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. For comparison, the critical densities of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) are $6 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respectively. The magnitude of the assumed density is way below the critical values. As a consequence, at the assumed densities of the ^{28}SiO -emitting shell, a high ^{28}SiO abundance along with an exceedingly high kinetic temperature would be required to strongly excite ^{28}SiO and produce the intense emissions observed. By assuming a relative ^{28}SiO abundance of 2.0×10^{-5} , a typical value for the inner envelope within the dust condensation radius ($\sim 10^{15}$ cm) around massive evolved stars (e.g. Bujarrabal et al., 1989), Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found that an excitation temperature of $T_{\text{ex}} \approx 55$ K is required to reproduce the observed peak intensity (brightness temperature of ~ 20 K) in the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) channel maps (Figure 4.3).

Figure 5.4 shows the modelled intensity in terms of brightness tempera-

ture adopting Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s physical parameters (density and abundance) as calculated by our code as described in Section 5.2. We found that the kinetic temperature has to be ~ 750 K, as shown in Figure 5.7, in order to excite ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) to brightness temperature comparable to observed values (~ 20 K) under the aforementioned assumed gas density and relative ^{28}SiO abundance. As we can see in Figure 5.6, the modelled excitation temperature (rotational temperature) for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) is about 87 K and 40 K at the inner and outer boundary respectively, clearly sub-thermal. This excitation temperature profile is comparable to 55 K as Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) obtained. However, Figure 5.7 shows that the excitation of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) causes population inversion for nearly the entire shell. Normally, such a high kinetic temperature is only found in the very inner regions of the envelope; for example, according to the radial temperature profile inferred by Teyssier et al. (2012) from multiple ^{12}CO transitions (^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) to ^{12}CO ($J = 6-5$), ^{12}CO ($J = 10-9$), and ^{12}CO ($J = 16-15$)), a kinetic temperature as high as 750 K is only found at around 3×10^{16} cm ($0''.40$), whereas over the radial range spanned by the postulated ^{28}SiO shell (from 9.00×10^{16} cm to 1.40×10^{17}) the kinetic temperature is much lower than that. By considering the balance of energy between heating and cooling of the molecular gases, Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) derived a maximum kinetic temperature of about 80 K for the postulated ^{28}SiO shell, and from models fitting the intensities of ^{12}CO transitions, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Teyssier et al. (2012) both found kinetic temperatures at most 260 K.

Even if this postulated ^{28}SiO shell may indeed correspond to a region having extremely elevated kinetic temperatures, possibly due to large-scale shocks as suggested by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001), the model of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) is still incomplete to explain all the features in the measured radial brightness temperature profiles and line ratio profile. First, as shown in Figure 5.4, the modelled brightness temperature profile for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) only gives a good fit to the observed profile at the peak position around $1''$.

However, no attempt was made to reproduce the extended ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission for the outer regions of the envelope, beyond a radius of $\sim 2''$ from the central star. Second, Figure 5.4 shows clearly that Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s model fails to predict ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission around $1''$. In particular, it overestimates the brightness temperature in the inner region ($\lesssim 1''.5$) by up to 50%, and underestimates in the outer part ($\gtrsim 2''$). The adopted high relative ^{28}SiO abundance of $\sim 10^{-5}$ (and hence high column density of ^{28}SiO) forces the emission to be closely optically thick (line ratio < 1.4) for the entire ^{28}SiO -emitting region. Therefore the model cannot explain the optically thin region (line ratio around 2) within $2''$ from the central star as we show in Figure 5.5. Third, the observed emission extends much further out (up to $\sim 6''$) than what is predicted in this model (up to $\sim 4''$). Therefore a more extended ^{28}SiO -emitting shell or more components beyond the current ^{28}SiO shell of different physical conditions are needed to explain the observed emission in the outer envelope.

5.4 Our Three-Zone Model of ^{28}SiO Emission

We can roughly identify three zones of different physical properties in the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420 as traced in ^{28}SiO . As hinted by the RADEX analysis described in Section 5.1, we can qualitatively infer the variation of gas density and relative abundance as a function of radius to reproduce the observed ^{28}SiO brightness temperature profiles shown in Figure 4.7 and the line ratio profile shown in Figure 4.8.

The inner zone, spanning from the star to $1''.5$, exhibits a relatively high line ratio of around 2.0 and centrally depressed ^{28}SiO emission in both transitions. As we have explained in Section 5.1, the ^{28}SiO column density must be relatively low in order to produce the optically thin regime as indicated by the relatively high line ratio above unity. Also, as we have argued based on critical

Figure 5.4: The modelled radial profile for brightness temperature for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) (red) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (blue) adopting the mass-loss rate of $\dot{M} = 3.6 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ and constant relative ^{28}SiO abundance of $[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$ as in (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001). The value of mass-loss rate, when assuming a constant expansion velocity of $V_{\text{exp}} = 38.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, leads to a gas density profile of $n_{\text{H}_2} = 1.42 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3} \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-2}$. The size of the single, detached ^{28}SiO -emitting shell is from $1''.2$ ($0.9 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$) to $1''.9$ ($1.4 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$). The gas kinetic temperature required to fit the observed emission peaks is about $T_{\text{kin}} = 750 \text{ K}$.

Figure 5.5: The modelled radial profile for the line brightness temperature ratio. Model parameters are the same as Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.6: The modelled radial profiles for the excitation temperatures of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) (red) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (blue), only showing the radial range of the ^{28}SiO -emitting shell. The adopted kinetic temperature is well above the plotted range and will be plotted in Figure 5.7. Model parameters are the same as Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.7: The adopted kinetic temperature is 750 K (dark). Similar to Figure 5.6, excitation temperatures of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) (red) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) (blue) are plotted. The negative values in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) indicate population inversion occurs for this set of model parameters. Model parameters are the same as Figure 5.4.

densities of ^{28}SiO , the gas density of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions here requires to be in the range of $\sim 10^{4.8} - 10^{5.3} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, a few times higher than that inferred for the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), which is $\sim 10^4 - 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. As compared to the other two zones, whatever the mechanism responsible for the density enhancement relative to ^{12}CO -emitting envelope, it is reasonable to expect that the density of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions decreases outwards. So we also predict the density of the inner zone to be higher than outer regions. Therefore, we expect the inner zone to have relatively high gas density and a low ^{28}SiO abundance.

The middle zone, spanning from $1''.5$ to $\sim 2''.5$, shows a line ratio slightly above unity and emission peaks for both ^{28}SiO rotational transitions. Our analysis in Section 5.1 suggests that the column density, and hence the relative abundance in this zone must be higher than the inner zone in order to produce a nearly optically thick regime and high brightness temperatures for both transitions. The gas density should be comparable to the critical densities (i.e. $\gtrsim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) so as to produce intense ^{28}SiO emission. The precise value of gas density, however, would then depend on the value of relative abundance which is constrained by both brightness temperatures and line ratio.

The outer zone, spanning from $\sim 2''.5$ to the outer edge of the envelope, shows the line ratio consistent to 1.0 and decreasing trends of the brightness temperature of both transitions. We expect the gas density should probably be close to critical values or slightly subcritical (i.e. $\sim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$). From the RADEX analysis in Section 5.1, the relative abundance of ^{28}SiO is better constrained by the magnitude of brightness temperatures which represents the strength of emission, rather than the line ratio which indicates an optically thick emission throughout this region of the envelope.

For the sake of simplicity and comparison, we base the geometry of our ^{28}SiO model on that of the ^{12}CO model suggested by Castro-Carrizo et al.

(2007) and Teyssier et al. (2012). When we compared the ^{28}SiO observations with the ^{12}CO as published by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), we found the structure of ^{28}SiO envelope is similar, in a global sense, to that traced in ^{12}CO molecules. First, as shown in Figure 4.7, at least for the transition ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$), the radial brightness temperature profiles for both ^{28}SiO and ^{12}CO molecules show a similar peak of emission at a radius of roughly $\sim 1''$, although ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) peaks further away at $\sim 2''$. Second, both ^{28}SiO (Figures 4.2 and 4.3) and ^{12}CO (Figures 2.6 and 2.7) channel maps show the similar extent of emission up to around $6'' - 8''$. As a starting point to model the ^{28}SiO emission, we therefore assume the same global three-zone structure for the ^{28}SiO -emitting region as the ^{12}CO envelope. We note that the inner radius of the ^{28}SiO -emitting shell as modelled in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) is much further away from the star than that of the inner shell in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s ^{12}CO model. However, as we analysed using RADEX result (also see Figure 5.2), the high line ratio implies that the gas density must be very high, instead of being approximated by an empty region, in the inner zone.

In addition, we adopt inverse square laws for the gas density profiles for each modelled zones. This is based on the assumption that the origin of ^{28}SiO -emitting gas is connected to that of ^{12}CO -emitting envelope, which makes the density of ^{28}SiO -emitting region, within each zone, being enhanced by a constant factor relative to the surrounding bulk envelope as traced in ^{12}CO .

5.4.1 Model Parameters of 3-Zone Model

Figures 5.8 and 5.9 show our calculated profiles for the brightness temperature and line ratio respectively. Figures 5.10 and 5.11 show the input molecular gas density and relative ^{28}SiO abundance profiles respectively. The parameters as a function of radius are also expressed below. The three zones correspond respectively to the inner ^{12}CO shell, the “gap” between the inner

and outer ^{12}CO shells that was modelled as an empty region, and the outer ^{12}CO shell in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007)'s model for the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope.

$$\frac{n_{\text{H}_2}}{\text{cm}^{-3}} = \begin{cases} 3.47 \times 10^4 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-2} & 0.25 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 1.24 \\ 2.17 \times 10^4 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-2} & 1.24 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 2.20 \\ 2.05 \times 10^5 \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right)^{-2} & 2.20 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 5.20 \\ 0.0 & \text{; otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2] = \begin{cases} 1.1 \times 10^{-6} \cdot \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) & 0.25 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 1.24 \\ 6.0 \times 10^{-6} & 1.24 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 2.20 \\ 4.8 \times 10^{-8} \cdot \left(4.8 - \frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) & 2.20 < \left(\frac{r}{10^{17} \text{ cm}}\right) \leq 4.80 \\ 0.0 & \text{; otherwise} \end{cases}$$

5.4.2 Inner Zone

For the inner zone, i.e. the region corresponding to the inner ^{12}CO shell in the model of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), we require a relatively low ^{28}SiO abundance and a high gas density. First of all, as we calculated in Section 5.3, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s very high ^{28}SiO abundance ($[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2] = 2 \times 10^{-5}$) does not provide a good fit to their ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) data over the entire radial range of ^{28}SiO emission. The reason Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) had to assumed a high ^{28}SiO abundance is to reproduce the observed brightness temperature under their assumed low molecular density (as that traced in ^{12}CO) for the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions. By adopting such a high abundance and low density, the envelope is in optically thick regime

Figure 5.8: Model fit of radial brightness temperature profiles under the three-zone model. The points are the observed data with uncertainties.

Figure 5.9: Model fit of radial line brightness temperature ratio profiles under the 3-zone model.

Figure 5.10: Molecular H_2 gas density profile of the 3-zone model.

Figure 5.11: Relative ^{28}SiO molecular abundance profile of the 3-zone model.

and the calculated line ratio have the value close to unity, inconsistent with our measured line ratio showing values of around 2 towards the central star, as shown in Figure 4.8. We emphasize that, although (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2001) adopted different radii for the ^{28}SiO -emitting shell than our inner zone, the ^{28}SiO column density in Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) model is so high that the line ratio does not depend much on the assumed size and position of the shell. In order to fit the observed high line ratio of around 2 in the inner envelope, we need the ^{28}SiO emission to be relatively optically thin. We therefore have to employ a low abundance for ^{28}SiO , of order 10^{-7} to get a sufficiently low ^{28}SiO column density.

In addition, in order to excite ^{28}SiO to produce significant amount of emission, we need the gas density to be above critical, i.e. $n_{\text{H}_2} \gtrsim 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, which corresponds a roughly a few (~ 3) times enhancement in the local molecular density in ^{28}SiO -emitting regions compared to the bulk traced in ^{12}CO . Given the same column density, a much higher density is impossible. As we have discussed in Section 5.1 and shown in Figures 5.1 and 5.2, the emission will then become more optically thin and hence line ratio will tend to an even higher value up to 4.0. The measured moderate optical thickness can be reconciled only if the relative abundance/column density of ^{28}SiO also increases. However, it would then produce a brightness temperature way too high than the observed. Therefore, the combination of relatively high (but not too high) gas density and low ^{28}SiO abundance is rather well-constrained to fit the brightness temperatures of both lines, as well as the line brightness temperature ratio of ~ 2 in the inner zone.

Figure 5.13 shows that both transition lines exhibit weak population inversion within the inner zone. From our calculation, negative excitation temperature occurs throughout the inner zone for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) and within $\lesssim 1''.5$ for ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). The inverted population here is found to be very weak and therefore strong amplification of radiative transfer

Figure 5.12: Excitation temperature profiles of the 3-zone model.

is not expected. This is consistent with the previous reports of non-detection of ^{28}SiO ground-state maser around IRC+10420 (e.g. Dickinson et al., 1978; Nyman et al., 1986, 1998; Nakashima & Deguchi, 2003). Theoretical prediction also expect weak population inversion for ground vibrational state ^{28}SiO masers because the collisional rate and radiative depopulation (from $v = 0$) rate are comparable (Kwan & Scoville, 1974). Weak masers for both ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0, v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1, v = 0$) around other evolved stars have been observed (e.g. Wright et al., 1995; Boboltz & Claussen, 2004), though not directly detected for IRC+10420.

Figure 5.13: Excitation temperature profiles at the inner region ($< 2''$) of the 3-zone model.

5.4.3 Outer Zone

The outer zone requires also a moderately high gas density, and a very low abundance. In Figure 4.7, we can see that the brightness temperatures of both transitions are much lower than other parts of the envelope, implying a relatively low ^{28}SiO column density. The line ratio there is slightly less than 1.0 as shown in Figure 4.8, corresponding to an emission regime close to optically thick.

Given the low ^{28}SiO column density as inferred from the low brightness temperatures in this zone, we have to reduce the gas density to subcritical values ($\lesssim 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) or otherwise the emission will become optically thin, thus leading to a line ratio higher than unity. On the other hand, we cannot adopt a much lower density (say 10^3 cm^{-3}). If the gas density is well below the critical densities of both lines, spontaneous de-excitation will dominate over collisional de-excitation. Cascades from higher levels will favour the emission in the lower transitions. As we calculate in Section 5.1 and show in Figures 5.1 and 5.2, this will result in a line ratio much lower than 1.0. Therefore the local gas density profile in this region is tightly constrained, within the range of $\sim 10^{4.0} - 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This is extremely enhanced by 1 – 2 orders of magnitude when compared to the bulk as traced in ^{12}CO , in which densities much lower than $\ll 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\ll 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ have been deduced by Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) and Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) respectively.

The relative ^{28}SiO abundance here, on the other hand, is not well-constrained by the low line ratio here, as indicated in Figure 5.2. Rather, with the gas density tightly constrained by the optically thick emission regime, and the ^{28}SiO column density constrained by the brightness temperatures, the ^{28}SiO abundance is then found to be $\lesssim 10^{-8}$, much lower (by at least one order of magnitude) than the inner zone. For verification, we tried to fit the outer zone with lower density and higher abundance (to keep the brightness temperatures

reasonably well-fit) but failed to obtain a better results on the line ratio. It should be cautioned that for region further out ($\gtrsim 4''$) in the outer zone, the uncertainties in the values of line ratio are relatively high compared to inner regions.

5.4.4 Middle Zone – the “Gap”

For the middle zone, corresponding to the modelled “gap” between the inner and outer ^{12}CO shells, we found that a low density region as inferred from ^{12}CO emission (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007; Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009) cannot explain the ^{28}SiO emission. From the radial brightness temperature profiles shown in Figures 4.7, there is no sign for a low-emission component beyond the first peak of emissions at around $2''$. From our simulation shown in Figure 5.14, if a zone of low density exists (for simplicity we modelled it as zero gas density), then the radial profiles for brightness temperatures will show a significant depressed emission at the radius $\sim 2''.5 = 1.9 \times 10^{17}$ cm. Such a local minimum in emission is not seen from the observed profiles in both transitions. Furthermore, the peaks in emission of both ^{28}SiO transitions will shift towards the central star, inconsistent to what we observed. Therefore we can conclude that the gas density of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions between the two ^{12}CO shells (i.e. within the inter-shell region) must be comparable to that of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions within each ^{12}CO shell. The variation of density of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions is smoother than that deduced from the diffuse envelope emitting in ^{12}CO .

We also found that the middle zone has different physical conditions than the inner and outer zones. The observed line ratio here is slightly above 1.0, meaning the ^{28}SiO emission is close to optically thick. For the same reason as the outer shell, it requires a gas density close to subcritical values, $\lesssim 10^{4.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. As we have explained in Section 5.1, a higher density can-

Figure 5.14: Modelled radial brightness temperature profiles under zero density in the middle zone between the two ^{12}CO shells. The gas density for the inner zone is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 1.78 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-2}$ and for the outer shell is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 2.76 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-2}$; and the ^{28}SiO relative abundance for the inner zone is $4.0 \times 10^{-6} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})$; and for the outer zone is $7.0 \times 10^{-8} \cdot (4.8 - r/10^{17} \text{ cm})$. The modelled profiles show a significantly depressed emission in the inter-shell region, which is not seen in observed profiles.

Figure 5.15: Modelled radial line ratio profile under zero density in the middle zone between the two ^{12}CO shells. Input parameters are described in Figure 5.14. The modelled profile does not fit the observed profiles for the entire inter-shell region.

not reproduce the optically thick emission unless for a high column density, which will predict significantly higher brightness temperatures than what we observed for this zone. For the gas density limited by the critical values, we found a high ^{28}SiO abundance of $[\text{SiO}]/[\text{H}_2] \sim 10^{-6}$ as compared to the inner and outer zones is required to reproduce the high brightness temperatures in this middle zone. As a result, the middle zone requires a relatively low gas density and high ^{28}SiO abundance as compared to the other zones.

Visual inspection of the radial profiles of brightness temperatures in Figure 4.7 and line ratio in Figure 4.8 does not show an obvious distinction between the middle and outer zones for radius beyond $1''.65 = 1.24 \times 10^{17}$ cm. Is it possible that these two zones can be modelled with a single profile of similar physical conditions? Figure 5.16 show the poor fits to the observed brightness temperatures when we modelled the envelope beyond $> 1''.65$ with single density and abundance profiles. As shown in Figure 5.17, the line ratio for radius $\gtrsim 3''$ falls below the observed values of about 1.0, which means the ^{28}SiO abundance adopted for this outer part is far too high and/or the gas density is too low. Therefore, the outer zone has to be distinguished from the middle zone in order to produce a reasonable fit to the data.

As we have shown in this Section, although in the ^{12}CO model of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) the mass-loss rate ceases abruptly between the two episodes of mass loss, thus resulting in a very low, if not zero, gas density between the inner and outer zones, we found that the gas density for ^{28}SiO -emitting regions in this zone between the two shells must be comparable to the other two zones. Furthermore, ^{28}SiO -emitting regions within this middle zone shows a slightly lower gas density and much higher ^{28}SiO abundance than those in the other two zones. In the next chapter, we will explore the natures of these ^{28}SiO -emitting regions and also re-examine our starting model assumption, which associates the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions with the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope and hence invokes a three-zone structure.

Figure 5.16: Model fit of radial brightness temperature profiles under a two-zone model: the inner zone and the combined middle and outer zone combined. The outer radius is reduced to $4''.67 = 3.5 \times 10^{17}$ cm. The gas density for the inner zone is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 3.47 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-2}$ and for the combined zone beyond is $n_{\text{H}_2} = 2.17 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-2}$; and the ^{28}SiO relative abundance for the inner zone is $1.1 \times 10^{-6} \cdot (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})$; and for the combined outer zone is constant at 3.0×10^{-6} .

Figure 5.17: Model fit of radial brightness temperature profiles under a two-zone model: the inner zone and the combined middle and outer zone combined. Input parameters are described in Figure 5.16.

Chapter 6

Interpretation and Discussion

As we have shown in Section 5.3, a single, detached, thin, spherical shell emitting in ^{28}SiO cannot by itself explain all the observed ^{28}SiO emission from the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420. This shell, assuming a relatively low gas density comparable to that deduced for the ^{12}CO -emitting regions, requires a highly elevated ^{28}SiO relative abundance of order comparable to that found in the inner envelopes around AGB stars ($\sim 10^{-5}$) and also a highly elevated kinetic temperature only expected at much inner regions of the envelope of IRC+10420 (~ 750 K) in order to reproduce the peak brightness temperatures of ^{28}SiO emission at radius $\sim 1''$. The most plausible physical origin of such a single large-scale ^{28}SiO -emitting shell with elevated ^{28}SiO abundance and kinetic temperature, as proposed by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001), is a large-scale shock as a result of an inner fast-moving outflow ploughing through an outer slower-moving outflow. During the process the gas and dust are heated up and hence ^{28}SiO is released into gas phase. We will discuss in Section 6.1 whether such interaction of outflows is possible on the basis of the global mass-loss history as inferred by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009).

As we can see in Chapter 4, ^{28}SiO emission is detected throughout the

entire envelope out to about $6''$. Therefore, in any case whether the large-scale shocks are possible, ^{28}SiO emission within and beyond the radial range of this proposed shock must be generated differently. As we have modelled in Section 5.4, we found the gas density responsible for the ^{28}SiO emission must be elevated as compared that for ^{12}CO emission. We will discuss in Section 6.2 whether the high density may explain ^{12}CO emission. Finding that this cannot be the case, we then explore the surface filling factor of the dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps with respect to the more diffuse ^{12}CO -emitting envelope.

In Section 6.3, we then explore the likely nature of these dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps. We found a possible connection of these clumps with the numerous dust knots detected with the *HST* (Humphreys et al., 1997; Tiffany et al., 2010) (also mentioned in Section 2.2). As we point out, the major weakness for such connection is the presence of a middle zone in which the physical conditions (such as gas density and ^{28}SiO abundance) of the ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps appear to be different to those from the inner and outer zones. The dust knots seen in scattered light, on the other hand, do not exhibit sign of different physical properties for the radial range of the middle zone in the ^{28}SiO model. Another major weakness of associating our ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps with dust knots seen in scattered light is that Tiffany et al. (2010) proposed an equatorial flow for the dust knots, whereas we found ^{28}SiO -emitting regions in a global spherical symmetry. We therefore critically examined the Tiffany et al. (2010)'s approach to derive the three-dimensional motions and spatial distributions of the dust knots. It turns out that a spherical symmetric distribution is even more likely than an equatorial flow in explaining some of the observed kinematics of the knots, despite some inconsistencies that are not addressed by any existing models. In Section 6.4, we re-examine our starting model motivation of such a middle zone and discuss the more likely distribution of the ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps. We conclude with a final model showing the more likely nature of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps and compare it with our initial

three-zone model.

6.1 A Thin, Detached ^{28}SiO -Emitting Shell

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) modelled their ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) channel maps in terms of a single, spherical, hollow shell spanning a radial range of 9×10^{16} cm ($1''.2$) to 1.4×10^{17} cm ($1''.87$). Assuming a constant mass-loss rate for the star of $3.6 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ as derived from single-dish ^{12}CO spectra, the resultant density of the shell is $\sim 2 \times 10^4$ cm^{-3} at its inner radius and $\sim 9 \times 10^3$ cm^{-3} at its outer radius. In this situation, to produce the observed high brightness temperature of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$), Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found that a high ^{28}SiO abundance (relative to hydrogen molecules) of 2×10^{-5} and a high kinetic temperature of about 750 K are required for the postulated shell. However, such a shell cannot reproduce the brightness temperature we measured for ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) over the same radial range. Instead, in Section 5.1, we showed that any such shell is required to have a density of $\gtrsim 6 \times 10^4$ cm^{-3} , nearly an order of magnitude higher than that inferred for the ^{12}CO -emitting gas over the same radial range, to reproduce both the measured ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) and ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) brightness temperatures. The required ^{28}SiO abundance is comparatively modest, $\sim 10^{-8} - 10^{-6}$, as is the required kinetic temperature of $\gtrsim 100$ K. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) speculate that their postulated spherical shell could be produced by a large-scale shock generated as a result of interactions between an inner faster-moving portion and an outer slower-moving portion of the expanding envelope of IRC+10420. Indeed, such a large-scale shock is expected to heat silicate dust grains and hence evaporate ^{28}SiO molecule into gas phase through sputtering. It should also compress the gas and hence significantly elevate the gas density. Given the mass-loss history of IRC+10420 subsequently inferred by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) from

^{12}CO channel maps, the mass-loss rate of the inner shell is much higher than that in the outer vacuum region. A higher mass-loss rate means a higher gas density in the outflow, which allows for stronger coupling between dust and gas. As a result, the radiatively-accelerated dust will transfer its momentum more efficiently to molecular gas, which then drive the gaseous outflow to a higher expansion velocity (e.g. Schöier & Olofsson, 2001). The strong correlation between mass-loss rate and outflow expansion velocity has been seen in both carbon-rich and oxygen-rich evolved stars (e.g. Schöier & Olofsson, 2001; Bladh et al., 2013). Therefore, we expect the inner high mass-loss ^{12}CO shell expands faster than the outer low mass-loss region. Since the proposed large-scale shock has a radial range from $1''.2$ to $1''.9$, overlapping the boundary of the inner shell and the vacuum region at $1''.65$, a large-scale shock is possible from the theoretical viewpoint.

However, even if such a large-scale shock exists, the postulated ^{28}SiO -emitting shell cannot by itself explain the ^{28}SiO emission for the entire radial range of the ^{28}SiO emission around IRC+10420. Specifically, interior to the postulated thin shell, the line ratio shows very different values to other parts in the envelope. This indicates there is significant amount of gas of different physical conditions in this “hollow” region in the model as compared to the other parts. In addition, exterior to the postulated ^{28}SiO -emitting shell, the emission of ^{28}SiO extends up to a radius of $\sim 4.5 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm} = 6''$.

6.2 Dense ^{28}SiO -Emitting Clumps

As we showed in Section 5.4, except for the inner zone, the ^{28}SiO emission throughout the outer envelope ($> 1''.65$) of IRC+10420 originates from gas that is at a significantly higher density than that inferred by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) for the ^{12}CO emission at the same radius from the star. Could the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope originate from

the same dense gas? Through a simple estimate using RADEX, we find that both the ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) emissions are optically thin in the models of Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009). If the density of the ^{12}CO -emitting gas is elevated to the values required in our model for the ^{28}SiO -emitting gas, then we find that the ^{12}CO column density and hence brightness temperatures in ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) would be much higher than observed. In addition, gas at such densities implies an average mass-loss rate of $10^{-3} - 10^{-2} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$. Such a high mass-loss rate is even higher than the current, non-erupting mass-loss rate ($10^{-3} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$) of η Carinae, which is among the most luminous stars as well as having among the highest mass-loss rates known in our Galaxy (Hillier et al., 2001). Therefore, we are led to the picture where *the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions originate from dense clumps embedded in a more diffuse envelope that emits the bulk of the ^{12}CO . These dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps exist throughout a large fraction of the observable extent of the ^{12}CO envelope.* Figure 6.1 shows a cartoon of the physical picture we have in mind.

Our model as described in Section 5.4 assumes that the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions occupies the same volume of space as the ^{12}CO -emitting regions, i.e. a filling factor of unity. If instead the ^{28}SiO emissions originate from localized dense clumps as we argue, then the volume filling factor of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions must therefore be considerably less than unity. Thus, to preserve the same column density in ^{28}SiO as derived in our model, the average ^{28}SiO abundance of the individual clumps must therefore be higher than derived in our model. That is, the model ^{28}SiO abundance is simply the product of the actual gas-phase ^{28}SiO abundance and the surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps. For a ^{28}SiO relative abundance in the range of $10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$, as typically found around the inner region (within $\sim 10^{15}$ cm) of oxygen-rich envelopes around AGB stars (González Delgado et al., 2003), the surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps is roughly $10^{-2} - 10^{-1}$ for the inner zone (i.e. the inner ^{12}CO shell), $10^{-1} - 1.0$ for the middle zone (i.e. the “gap”

Figure 6.1: Illustration showing our physical picture for the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420. Dense, clumpy ^{28}SiO -emitting regions (as represented by blue dots) are embedded within the more diffuse envelope that emits the bulk of ^{12}CO (as represented by the violet region). As we will show in Sections 6.3 and 6.4, the distribution of dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps is not uniform throughout the envelope – a much higher filling factor is predicted towards regions closer to the central star than regions beyond $\sim 3''$.

between ^{12}CO shells), and $10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$ for the outer zone (i.e. the outer ^{12}CO shell). (The volume filling factor can, and is likely to be, considerably smaller than the surface filling factor.) If instead, the surface filling factor of dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps is constant throughout the envelope, then the average ^{28}SiO abundance of the clumps must change with radius. That is, the ^{28}SiO abundance of the dense clumps in the middle zone must be 1 – 2 orders of magnitude higher than that in the adjacent inner and outer zones. Of course, in reality, both the surface filling factor and ^{28}SiO abundance can change with radius.

We can obtain a greater insight on the surface filling factor as well as temperature of these dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps by comparing the brightness temperatures of ^{28}SiO with that of ^{12}CO . As we can see from Figure 4.7, both ^{28}SiO transitions attain peak brightness temperature of 15 – 20 K at radii of $\sim 1'' - 2''$. By comparison, over the same radial range, both the ^{12}CO ($J = 1-0$) and ^{12}CO ($J = 2-1$) transitions attain peak brightness temperatures of only 3 – 10 K (Castro-Carrizo et al., 2007, Figure 10) (Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009, Figure 14). In this radial range, the ^{28}SiO emission is close to optically thick as we mention in Section 5.1. By comparison, as mentioned above, simple RADEX calculation shows that the ^{12}CO emission is optically thin, having an optical depth of < 0.1 . The factor of $\sim 2 - 5$ higher brightness temperatures of ^{28}SiO compared with ^{12}CO therefore requires a surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps of approximately 0.2 – 0.5, assuming that both the ^{28}SiO and ^{12}CO gas have the same kinetic temperatures. If the ^{28}SiO -emitting gas is at a higher kinetic temperature, then the surface filling factor of dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps can be correspondingly lower.

6.3 Nature of ^{28}SiO -Emitting Clumps

Is there any independent evidence for dense clumps distributed throughout (up to a radius of $6'' = 4.5 \times 10^{17}$ cm) the envelope of IRC+10420, as is required in our model to produce the observed ^{28}SiO emission? Interestingly, as shown in Figures 2.3 and 2.5, observations with the *HST* by Humphreys et al. (1997) and Tiffany et al. (2010) reveal numerous compact dust features seen in reflected light. Humphreys et al. (1997) and Tiffany et al. (2010) refer to these compact dust features using terms as such knots, arcs, and jets; so as not to confuse with our postulated ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps, we shall henceforth refer to all these compact dust features as simply dust knots. These dust knots are detectable in projection over the same radial range as the ^{12}CO -emitting and ^{28}SiO -emitting envelope from $\sim 0''.5$ to $\sim 6''$. We therefore reason that these dust knots correspond to the clumps that we postulate to emit in ^{28}SiO .

An important problem, however, arises when relating our postulated ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps with the optical dust knots observed with the *HST*. Tiffany et al. (2010) have deduced the three-dimensional distribution and speeds of the dust knots by comparing *HST* images of IRC+10420 at two different epochs, the first taken in April 1996 and the second in March 2008. They identified about 40 dust knots common to both epochs, and were therefore able to deduce the transverse velocities for these dust knots (assuming a distance to the star of 5 kpc). Ten of these knots have radial velocities measured in September 1999 by Humphreys et al. (2002). By combining the inferred transverse and radial velocities of these knots, Tiffany et al. (2010) deduced that all these knots are travelling essentially in the plane of the sky within an angle of $\leq 12^\circ$, and most of them move at speeds of $\sim 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (with one exception of only 17 km s^{-1}). Because a number of the other dust knots also have high transverse velocities as we show in Figure 6.7, Tiffany et al. (2010) argue that all the dust knots are ejected at high velocities along essentially the plane of the

sky.

As we explain in the following, there is a serious flaw in the interpretation made by Tiffany et al. (2010) for the spatial distribution of the dust knots. First, we describe how the radial velocities of the dust knots are inferred. As shown in Figure 6.2, Humphreys et al. (2002) obtained $H\alpha$ spectra for numerous knots lying within two long slits separated by $0''.42$ across the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420. As we mentioned above, among the forty dust knots for which Tiffany et al. (2010) derived transverse velocities between two *HST* epochs, ten lie within these two slits, allowing their three-dimensional motions to be derived. The observed $H\alpha$ spectra from each knot is not produced by the knot itself, but constitutes reflected light from the inner regions of the envelope where $H\alpha$ emission is produced. Figure 6.3 shows the central $H\alpha$ velocity as measured for each knot within the six shaded regions of the slits as shown in Figure 6.2. As shown in Figure 6.4, the $H\alpha$ line emitting from the star does not reach us directly. Instead the emission is reflected from the dust knots and therefore $H\alpha$ line is Doppler shifted (relative to that from $H\alpha$ line-forming region) due to two effects: (1) line-of-sight component of the expansion velocity away from us (V_z , the green velocity vector pointing to the right) and (2) radial expansion of the entire envelope (including the dust knots) away from IRC+10420 at a speed of V_{exp} (the blue velocity vector). In addition to these components, the star is moving away from us at a systemic velocity of $V_0 = +74 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Therefore, the observed $H\alpha$ line reflected by the dust knots is redshifted by three components, and the total measured Doppler shift is expressed as: $V_{\text{Dopp}} = V_0 + V_{\text{exp}} + V_z$. Figure 6.3 shows a general trend of increasing Doppler velocity V_{Dopp} of the knots with increasing position along the slit, and therefore also projected distance from IRC+10420. Assuming (1) the same expansion velocity V_{exp} for all the dust knots and (2) a linearly increasing trend of Doppler velocity with slit position (i.e. dashed lines shown in Figure 6.5), the dust knots would be located along the loci drawn in Figure 6.6. The points (z, x) on the loci represent the expected positions of the knots along

Figure 6.2: The two slit positions lying on the envelope of IRC+10420 as imaged by (Humphreys et al., 2002). Slit 1 lies across the central star along the southwest to northeast axis and slit 2 lies in parallel to slit 1 at a displacement of $0''.42$ towards southeast. The six grey boxes represent the positions where $H\alpha$ line profiles are sampled (Taken from Figure 12 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

the slit x and along the line of sight z (with respect to the central star). The dashed lines drawn in Figure 6.5 are mathematically simple representations of the knots which help us to understand the general spatial distribution (z, x) of these knots (i.e. the loci). Different loci correspond to different assumed expansion velocities (V_{exp}) as indicated in Figure 6.6. As this figure shows, for larger assumed expansion velocities, the knots are located closer along our line of sight. We will show in Appendix C how to derive the spatial distribution of knots (z, x) from the Doppler velocity measurement under an assumed expansion velocity.

Figure 6.3: Measured Doppler velocities, V_{Dopp} , along the two slit positions. Filled circles represent knots measured by slit 1 which passes through IRC+10420 and crosses represent those measured by slit 2 which is located about $0''.42$ in parallel and southeast from slit 1. Open squares represent the measurements across an arc measured by slit 1 at about $1'' - 2''$ northeast from the star (Data points taken from Figure 9 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

Figure 6.4: Illustration showing how is the measured Doppler velocity V_{Dopp} related to the (1) the systemic velocity of IRC+10420 of V_0 , (2) the expansion velocity, V_{exp} , of the dust knots radially away from IRC+10420, and (3) the line-of-sight component of the expansion velocity, V_z .

An example of how the positions of the dust knots are computed, we consider the dust knot labelled A in Figure 6.5. This dust knot is located at a slit position of $x = 1''.7$ and has a measured Doppler velocity of $V_{\text{Dopp}} = 107 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Assuming an expansion velocity of $V_{\text{exp}} = 50 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, the line-of-sight component of the expansion velocity, V_z , is therefore $V_z = V_{\text{Dopp}} - V_{\text{exp}}(x) - V_0 = (107 - 50 - 74) \text{ km s}^{-1} = -17 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Thus, the knot must be moving towards us with a radial velocity of 17 km s^{-1} . The transverse component of the expansion velocity, $V_x = \sqrt{V_{\text{exp}}^2 - V_z^2} = \sqrt{50^2 - (-17)^2} = 47.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Because the transverse component of the expansion velocity is much higher than the radial component, this knot must be moving quite close to the plane of the sky. Indeed, the motion of the knot makes at a large angle of 70° with our line of sight. This knot is located at the line-of-sight position $z = V_z/V_x \cdot x = -17/47 \cdot 1''.7 = -0''.61$, as indicated with letter A in Figure 6.6.

Tiffany et al. (2010) adopted an entirely different interpretation for the Doppler measurements of Humphreys et al. (2002). Rather than a constant expansion velocity, Tiffany et al. (2010) assume a linearly increasing expansion velocity as a function of slit position, $V_{\text{exp}}(x)$ (Humphreys, private communications). This assumption implies a Hubble flow for the knots in which knots further out are moving faster, as would be the case if all the knots are ejected during a single explosive event. Specifically, Tiffany et al. (2010) assumed a Hubble flow of the form indicated by the dashed lines in Figure 6.5, corresponding to $V_{\text{exp}}(x) = 20 \text{ km/s/arcsec} \cdot |x|$ (for the northeast side) and $V_{\text{exp}}(x) = 6 \text{ km/s/arcsec} \cdot |x|$ (for the southwest side). In this picture, the expansion velocity of knot A is 34 km s^{-1} . The radial component of its expansion velocity $V_z = V_{\text{Dopp}} - V_{\text{exp}}(x) - V_0 = (107 - 20 \times 1.7 - 74) \text{ km s}^{-1} = -1 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, whereas the transverse component of its expansion velocity $V_x = \sqrt{V_{\text{exp}}^2 - V_z^2} \approx 34 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This knot would therefore be travelling close to the plane of the sky. In brief, if the expansion velocity V_{exp} strictly follows a Hubble flow as indicated by the dashed lines in Figure 6.5, then the radial

Figure 6.5: Same as 6.3. Dashed line represents the linear fit to the Doppler velocities of measured knots as a function of position along the slits. The fits at the northeast and southwest sides have slopes of 20 km/s/arcsec and -6 km/s/arcsec respectively (Taken from Figure 9 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

component of expansion velocity V_z is just the deviation of the knots from the dashed line. Because the deviations are relatively small, the radial velocity is always much smaller than the expansion velocity, and hence all the knots must be moving relatively close to the plane of sky. Therefore, Tiffany et al. (2010)'s conclusion, that the knots are distributed on a pole-on viewing equatorial disk, is indeed an implicit assumption of the Hubble flow that they adopt to interpret the Doppler measurements of the knots.

There is, however, a contradiction in the way Tiffany et al. (2010) interpreted the Doppler measurements of Humphreys et al. (2002). The knots with inferred three-dimensional motions are all located within a projected radius of $2''.0$ from IRC+10420 (see Tables 2 and 3 Tiffany et al., 2010). As shown

in Figure 6.5, for the assumed Hubble flow, the expansion velocities of these knots measured must be $V_{\text{exp}} < (130 - 74) \text{ km s}^{-1} = 56 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. By comparison, the typical transverse velocities that Tiffany et al. (2010) derived for ten of these knots are $\sim 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (see Table 3 of Tiffany et al., 2010). This leads to the situation where the projected transverse velocity is a factor of 2 higher than the expansion velocity, which is a clear contradiction. Indeed, as we plot in Figure 6.7, since the knots move in extremely high transverse velocity up to $\sim 220 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, it is impossible to find a model, whether Hubble flow or constant expansion, with expansion velocity less than that to simultaneously explain both measurements of transverse and radial velocities.

Tiffany et al. (2010) measured relatively high transverse velocities for many of the knots, and argued qualitatively that most of the knots must be moving close to the plane of the sky. This argument, however, may be subjected to selection effects. As shown in their Table 2 (Tiffany et al., 2010), the estimated transverse velocity spans a wide range, from the detectability limit of $\sim 15 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ to above 200 km s^{-1} . Selection effect is possible in which only knots with noticeable transverse motion can be identified and hence with the three-dimensional motion estimated. Their approach to search for moving knots is by blinking the images from two epochs, for shifts of the knots with four different filter combinations. By this approach, only knots moving along the equatorial plane typically with highest transverse velocities are easily identified. Tiffany et al. (2010), however, did not mention if there are any other knots without measurable angular shifts between two epochs, so we cannot tell if the selection effect has been addressed. If we, on the other hand, assume the envelope expansion velocity of $\sim 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ as inferred from molecular lines, for knots moving along directions within $\sim \sin^{-1}(15/40) = 22^\circ$ from the line-of-sight direction, their transverse displacements between the two epochs of *HST* observations cannot be spatially resolved.

Tiffany et al. (2010)'s interpretation of the Doppler velocity measure-

Figure 10 of Humphreys, Davidson and Smith (2002)

Figure 6.6: Spatial loci with respect to the stellar position corresponding to the linear trends in the measured Doppler velocities as shown in Figure 6.5 for different envelope expansion velocities V_{exp} . The segment of curve at position along slit of $x \sim 1'' - 2''$ represent the arc structure that the slit measured across. It is also represented by open squares in Figure 6.5. The line of sight is from the left to the right (Similar to Figure 10 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

Figure 6.7: Knots with transverse velocity measured and their projected radius on the plane of sky from IRC+10420. The data are taken from Table 2 of Tiffany et al. (2010). Only knots located in the inner envelope of IRC+10420 within a projected radius of $\sim 2''.2$ are selected in this plot. Two dashed lines indicating the expansion velocities of 38 km s^{-1} (as traced in molecular emissions) and 60 km s^{-1} (as we model for the Doppler velocities) are drawn for comparison.

ments is not the unique explanation. Here, we show that measurements of the Doppler velocities are also compatible with a more-or-less uniform distribution of the knots in a spherically symmetric envelope. Instead of assuming a mathematically convenient function of $V_{\text{Dopp}}(x)$, we make a physical interpretation that the spatial distribution of the knots follows spherical symmetry in which only knots lying on the near-side of the spherical distribution are measured by the slit. From the assumed spatial distribution, we can infer the predicted Doppler velocity measurement along the slits, $V_{\text{Dopp}}(x)$. The steps of derivation are just the reverse of Humphreys et al. (2002)'s derivation (as presented in Appendix C). Figure 6.8 shows the fitting to the measured Doppler velocity along the slits under this assumption of the spatial distribution. Figure 6.9 shows the assumed spatial distribution of the knots along a spherical surface of radius $1''.6$, and expanding at $V_{\text{exp}} = 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. Only knots located along the near-side are measured by the slits. In this scenario, the dust clumps are moving through the more diffuse ^{12}CO -emitting envelope with a relative velocity of $\sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. By comparison, the sound speed in the molecular gas of a typical kinetic temperature $\sim 10^1 - 10^2 \text{ K}$ is less than 1 km s^{-1} . The dust knots are therefore moving supersonically through the diffuse envelope. Thus, the strong shock is expected to be generated at the front surface of the clumps, thereby presumably heat up the silicate dust grains significantly and release frozen ^{28}SiO into gas phase. In addition, the shocks are expected to compress the gas, creating an environment in which ^{28}SiO can be strongly collisionally excited.

However, there are two major weaknesses in this interpretation. Despite a possibly more physically-motivated model in explaining the Doppler velocities, the extremely high transverse velocities as inferred by Tiffany et al. (2010) cannot be explained by our model. Indeed, any models which stick to a low expansion velocity ($\ll 100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) as traced in molecular gas cannot explain the high transverse velocities. Even if we assume the lower bound of the distance estimate of IRC+10420 (i.e. 3.5 kpc instead of 5 kpc), the inferred trans-

Figure 6.8: Same as Figure 6.5. The solid parabola represents our fit to the Doppler velocity of measured knots as a function of position along the slits for a spherically symmetric model. The model spherical envelope has a radius of $1''.6$ and constant expansion velocity of 60 km s^{-1} (Data points taken from Figure 9 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

verse velocities may only be reduced by at most 30%. Moreover, if the ^{28}SiO molecules are released at the fronts where the fast-moving knots ($\sim 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) interact with the diffuse gas envelope ($< 40 \text{ km s}^{-1}$), then the velocities of ^{28}SiO molecules should trace a range of about $40 - 60 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. As we can compare the channel maps of ^{28}SiO (Figures 4.1 and 4.2) with those of ^{12}CO (Figures 2.6 and 2.7), there is no evidence that the ^{28}SiO emission extends to significantly higher velocities than the ^{12}CO .

Figure 10 of Humphreys, Davidson and Smith (2002)

Figure 6.9: Spatial distribution of the knots with respect to the stellar position expected for a spherically symmetric distribution of radius $1''.6$. This distribution is independent of the expansion velocity as assumed in our model. The line of sight is from the left to the right. Only knots located along the near-side of the spherical distribution can be observed (Similar to Figure 10 of Humphreys et al., 2002).

6.4 A Two-Zone Model

In our model for the ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps described in Section 5.4, the circumstellar envelope is divided into three zones that correspond to the inner and outer ^{12}CO shells separated by a relatively vacuous region that produces little ^{12}CO emission. The ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps in the middle, relatively vacuous ^{12}CO -emitting zone are required to have 1 – 2 orders of magnitude higher surface filling factor of clumps and/or ^{28}SiO abundance than those in the inner and outer zones. However, a simple inspection of the *HST* images shown in Figures 2.3 or 2.5 reveal no such intermediate zone having a significantly different surface filling factor of clumps.

Here, we re-examine whether the three-zone model as modelled in Section 5.4 is necessary to reproduce the observed ^{28}SiO emission. As we mentioned in Section 5.4, the motivation of the three-zone model comes from the resemblance between the structure of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions and that of ^{12}CO -emitting envelope on a global scale, as shown in Figures 4.1, 4.3, 2.6 and 2.7. Therefore we adopt the three-zone geometry similar to those used by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) to model the ^{12}CO emission, as the initial guess to model the ^{28}SiO emission. If the ^{28}SiO emission is produced by dense clumps embedded within the more diffuse gas responsible for ^{12}CO emission as we believe, the physical conditions for ^{28}SiO emission are then separated from those for ^{12}CO emission. Whereas the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope traces the global mass-loss history of IRC+10420, the dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps are likely ejected from localized regions in the stellar atmosphere, or shocked regions due to interaction between outflows. These localized phenomena in the stellar atmosphere or some extended radii of circumstellar envelope are not necessary tied to the episodic variation of the global mass loss from the star. Therefore the motivation to model the ^{28}SiO emission as originating from three separate zones is removed.

A simple visual inspection of the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) line ratio profile in Figure 4.8 indicates at least two distinct zones – an inner zone of radius $\lesssim 2''$ where the line ratio is significantly above unity, and the region beyond where the line ratio is approximately unity. The comparison in line ratio provides us motivation that the physical conditions in the two zones are different. The ^{28}SiO emission from the inner zone is optically thin while that from the outer zone is optically thick.

Indeed, as described in the following, we can model the ^{28}SiO emission in terms of a two-zone model. First, the density profile of the three-zone model as shown in Figure 5.10 exhibits variation within 1 – 2 orders of magnitude throughout the envelope. This motivates a single, smooth power-law profile for the density in which the density scale and power-law index are model parameters. We also divide the envelope into two different constant abundance zones, where the boundary between two zones is a parameter. Figure 6.10 shows the density profile given by $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3} \times (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-0.7}$ in our two-zone model. Figure 6.11 shows an abundance profile that is divided into (1) an inner zone between $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}$ ($0''.67$) and $2.35 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$ ($3''.13$) having a higher ^{28}SiO abundance of 1.25×10^{-6} and, (2) an outer zone between $2.35 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$ ($3''.13$) and $4.20 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}$ ($5''.60$) having a lower abundance of 6.00×10^{-8} . As shown in Figures 6.12 and 6.13, these parameters are able to reasonably reproduce the measured brightness temperatures and line ratio profiles. The largest deviation between the model and data occurring at radii near $2''$. We have also tried to model the abundance with simpler, smooth profiles including constant, linearly decreasing, or power-law functions. In all these one-zone models, we could not obtain a reasonable fit to the data.

Our two-zone model for the ^{28}SiO emission requires the surface filling factor and/or ^{28}SiO abundance to be 1 – 2 orders of magnitude higher between radii of $0''.67$ and $3''.13$, as compared with regions beyond. This in general agrees with the optical images taken by Humphreys et al. (1997) and Tiffany

Figure 6.10: Molecular H₂ gas density profile, adopting a power-law profile of $2.3 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3} \times (r/10^{17} \text{ cm})^{-0.7}$.

Figure 6.11: Relative ^{28}SiO molecular abundance profile. The inner zone has an abundance of 1.25×10^{-6} from 5×10^{16} cm ($0''.67$) to 2.35×10^{17} cm ($3''.13$); and the outer zone has an abundance of 6.00×10^{-8} from 2.35×10^{16} cm ($3''.13$) to 4.20×10^{17} cm ($5''.60$).

Figure 6.12: Radial brightness temperature profiles for the two-step abundance and power-law density profile.

Figure 6.13: Radial line ratio profile for the two-step abundance and power-law density profile.

et al. (2010) in which small-scale clumps are primarily found within a radius of $\sim 2''.5$ from the star. However, comparison to the optical images may be subject to bias that the gas density and intensity of stellar emission generally fall off with radius, thus making the scattered light by clumpy regions less readily detected in the outer envelope. This two-zone model also shows that the density of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps does not necessarily fall off with radius as $1/r^2$, as in the case of free expansion of gas away from the star. We consider two possible formation mechanisms of these dense ^{28}SiO clumps and their implications in the context of the radial density profile. If as postulated by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) that the ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps are formed due to shocks at the radii where the emission is seen, then the density enhancement relative to the more diffuse gas emitting in ^{12}CO would vary dramatically with radius. For example, we estimate from Figure 6.10 that shocks will only compress the gas by a factor of at most ~ 3 within the inner ^{12}CO shell as modelled by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), but by a large factor of > 100 within the vacuous inter-shell region. In other words, the interactions between the outflows in the envelope would require very specific conditions depending on the radius in order to reconcile the smooth variation of density (varies as $r^{-0.7}$) and ^{28}SiO abundance of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions within the inner zone ($0''.67 - 3''.13$). On the other hand, if all the ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps are ejected from the stellar atmosphere, then the density profile implies that the clumps are restricted from free expansion for which an inverse square law is expected. This can happen if the clumps are permeated by magnetic fields. Indeed, Tiffany et al. (2010) argued that large-scale magnetic fields may be responsible to constrain the free expansion of hot gas (which they referred as “bubbles”) ejected from the star.

Chapter 7

Summary and Future Work

7.1 Summary

The main goal of the thesis is to better understand the nature of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions in the circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420. IRC+10420 is a rare type of evolved stars which exhibit change in apparent spectral type from late F to, at least, mid A in just 30 years. The peculiar behaviour is now believed to be a result of the expansion of an optically thick wind around the star, thus exposing the hotter interior layer of the wind. A distance of 5 kpc is widely accepted for the star in recent literature. The large distance leads to the inference that the star is among the most luminous star in the Galaxy of its spectral type. With the spectral type of around mid A and very high luminosity of about $10^5 - 10^6 L_{\odot}$, IRC+10420 is classified as a yellow hypergiant, among the very few stars known to be in transition from a post-red supergiant to a luminous blue variable, Wolf-Rayet star or even a supernova.

The circumstellar envelope of IRC+10420, presumably ejected when it was a red supergiant, provides a glance at its mass-loss history over the past few thousand years. Molecular gas in the envelope as traced in CO emission has

been imaged by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009). Their high resolution images in general show spherical symmetry on a global scale and centrally depressed emission. Detailed radiative transfer modelling of the radial brightness temperature profiles provide us a way to infer the gas density, and hence the mass-loss rate over the past few thousand years. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007) and Dinh-V-Trung et al. (2009) modelled the mass-loss of IRC+10420 as coming from two major mass-loss episodes of mass-loss rate $\dot{M} \sim 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$, separated by a period relatively low mass-loss rate of $\dot{M} < 10^{-5} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$.

Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) has imaged and modelled the ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) transition from IRC+10420's circumstellar envelope. Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) found, very surprisingly, strong ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission which peaks at an extended radius of $\sim 1''$. To explain the peak emission, Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) proposed a thin, spherical, hollow ^{28}SiO -emitting shell located near the peak ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission. They suggest a large-scale shock as a result from a faster-moving outflow ploughing through an exterior slower outflow. The shock then heat the dust grains to release ^{28}SiO into gas phase and also compress the gas to allow significant emission from ^{28}SiO molecule.

To better constrain the gas density and ^{28}SiO relative abundance in the envelope, and from those to infer the nature and origin of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions, we observed ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission with the VLA. We reduced the interferometric data and reconstructed the high-spatial resolution channel maps. The maps are convolved to the same spatial and gridded to the same spectral resolutions as the previous channel maps in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) for comparison.

The major findings in our observation in ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission, and the following radiative transfer modelling in both ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$)

and ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) brightness temperatures are summarized as follows.

1. The channel maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission are in general similar to those of ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). Both transition showing a globally spherically symmetric envelope, highly extended up to $\sim 6'' = 4.5 \times 10^{17}$ cm = 30000 AU from IRC+10420.
2. The maps of ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission show a similar central depression as ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$). A major difference is that ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission peaks at $\sim 2''$, slightly further away from where ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$) emission peaks ($\sim 1''$).
3. The line ratio in brightness temperatures close to the star within a radius of $\sim 2''$ is in optically thin regime of emission; while that beyond $\sim 2''$ is in optically thick regime.

Combining the radial brightness temperature profiles of our observed ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) emission and Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s result in ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$), we calculated the line ratio ^{28}SiO ($J = 2-1$, $v = 0$)/ ^{28}SiO ($J = 1-0$, $v = 0$) as a function of radius from star. This quantity provides us very useful constraints on the plausible ranges of gas density and ^{28}SiO abundance for our radiative transfer modelling of the ^{28}SiO emission. In the modelling, we used the radiative transfer code developed by Dinh-V-Trung & Nguyen-Q-Rieu (2000) and obtained the following results.

1. We first model with the parameters provided by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001) to test if their thin and hollow ^{28}SiO -emitting shell can explain both ^{28}SiO emissions. We found that Castro-Carrizo et al. (2001)'s single ^{28}SiO -emitting shell requires highly elevated gas kinetic temperature (up to 750 K) and ^{28}SiO abundance ($\sim 10^{-5}$) in order to reproduce the peak

brightness temperatures of both ^{28}SiO transitions. In addition, the single shell at $\sim 1''$ is insufficient to explain ^{28}SiO emission beyond $3''$.

2. If we assume that the origin of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions is associated with that of ^{12}CO -emitting regions in the envelope of IRC+10420, we found that the gas density of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions is greatly enhanced compared to ^{12}CO -emitting region. The surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions, assuming a constant ^{28}SiO abundance of $\sim 10^{-6}$, are comparatively low of about $10^{-3} - 10^{-1}$, except for the relatively tenuous region between the two ^{12}CO shells in which the surface filling factor is highly elevated to about 10^{-1} to unity.
3. If we do not assume any connection between ^{28}SiO -emitting and ^{12}CO -emitting regions, then we find that there are at least two zones of different physical conditions – an inner zone with much higher surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions and/or ^{28}SiO abundance (by about 20 times) than the outer zone. The gas density is also elevated to $\sim 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, compared to $10^3 - 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ as found in the ^{12}CO -emitting envelope.
4. No matter which assumption we used, the gas density of ^{28}SiO -emitting region must be very high compared to the ^{12}CO -emitting region, from a few factors in the inner envelope to about 2 orders of magnitudes in the outer envelope. We found that the ^{12}CO emission cannot be reproduced with such elevated gas densities.

Therefore, we conclude the nature of ^{28}SiO -emitting regions as dense clumps embedded within the more diffuse gas envelope emitting the bulk of ^{12}CO . The ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps exist throughout the observable extent of $\sim 6''$.

Finally, for the origin of the dense ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps, we found that clumpiness has been observed in the *HST* images (e.g. Humphreys et al., 1997; Tiffany et al., 2010). Therefore we speculate a possible connection between the

^{28}SiO -emitting clumps and the bright optical knots. We make the following interpretations.

1. Dense ^{28}SiO -emitting regions come from the interacting fronts between the faster-moving bright dust knots as seen in the optical (e.g. Humphreys et al., 1997; Tiffany et al., 2010) and the slower-moving diffuse molecular gas envelope.
2. The relative velocity of $\sim 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ of such interaction is high enough to create strong shock, thus releasing frozen ^{28}SiO from dust grains into gas phase and also compress the gas to an elevated density.
3. Our two-zone model in which the surface filling factor of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps is higher within a radius of $\sim 3''$ is consistent with the distribution of these optical dust knots which are primarily found within $\sim 2''.5$.

7.2 Future Work

Although we deduced the general nature of the ^{28}SiO -emitting regions as originating from dense clumps embedded within the more diffuse ^{12}CO -emitting envelope, a deeper understanding of the nature of these clumps is still not available. Therefore, we suggest the following future work.

1. Observations of high density tracers such as HCN or higher transitions of SiO molecules can provide a direct proof of the existence of dense clumps throughout the envelope of IRC+10420. Indeed, we have proposed and observed the HCN ($J = 3-2$), ^{28}SiO ($J = 6-5$) and ^{29}SiO ($J = 6-5$) transitions with the Combined Array for Research in Millimeter-wave Astronomy (CARMA). The critical densities of these transitions are of order $10^{6.9} - 10^{7.8} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, high enough to detect much denser regions in

the envelope. We will then need to reduce the data and infer the density and molecular abundances through modelling.

2. Observations with higher transitions of SiO can provide better constraints on the gas kinetic temperature. As we suggest for the origins of ^{28}SiO -emitting clumps as coming from shocks, the gas kinetic temperature is expected to be elevated. However, as we mentioned, the two low- J ^{28}SiO transitions are insensitive to the high temperature (of $10^1 - 10^2$ K throughout the envelope. Therefore we need direct evidence to probe the gas kinetic temperature in dense gas. For example, with the Submillimeter Array (SMA) of frequency ranging from 230 GHz to 690 GHz, we may be able to search for high SiO transitions from $J = 5-4$ up to $J = 16-15$, with excitation energies corresponding to about 30 – 280 K.

3. High sensitivity observations of the dense gas can trace the spatial distribution of clumps, especially for the outer envelope where the emission is weaker. As our model suggest, the surface filling factor of dense clumps is much higher in the inner envelope, and falls off rapidly in the outer envelope. Although optical images seem to be consistent with such a trend, they may be subjected to the distance effect on the intensity of stellar emission. Therefore we need higher sensitivity images to obtain a more accurate account on how the dense gas is distributed throughout the envelope, and from that to infer the history of dynamical instability of the star and perhaps any possible axis-symmetry as suggested in the literature. For example, we may use the Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) to trace the dense SiO-emitting clumps at the transition $J = 6-5$. As we found the emission at the outer envelope is close to optically thick, the kinetic temperature for the clumps would be around 30 – 50 K. With the spectral resolution of 1 km s^{-1} , and spatial resolution of $0''1$ (which is the typical size of dust knots seen

in the optical), we may obtain a sensitivity of less than 3.5 K with an hour of observation.

Appendix A

Circumstellar Extinction as Traced in ^{12}CO

The value of circumstellar extinction, A_V , can be estimated from the optical depth of the molecular hydrogen gas (H_2) along the line of sight, which can be shown below to be proportional to the column density. As ^{12}CO best traces molecular hydrogen gas (H_2) in the Galaxy and circumstellar environment, the column density can be inferred by modelling the envelope traced in ^{12}CO emission, as described in Section 2.3.

The definitions and adopted values of the parameters are as follows.

Extinction efficiency at V band, $Q_V \approx 1.5$ (Li, 2005)

Weighted averaged radius of the assumed spherical grains, $a = 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ (calculated from MRN model, Mathis et al., 1977; Hildebrand, 1983)

Mass density of typical graphite grains, $\rho_s = 2.25 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ (Hildebrand, 1983)

Mass of hydrogen molecules, $m_{\text{H}_2} = 3.3474 \times 10^{-24} \text{ g}$

Dust-to-gas number ratio, $\psi = 0.005$ (assumed)

Optical depth at V band, τ_V

Number density of dust, n_d

Number density of molecular hydrogen gas, n_{H_2}

Column density of molecular hydrogen gas, N_{H_2}

$$\begin{aligned}
A_V &= \frac{5}{2} \cdot \log_{10}(e) \cdot \tau_V \\
&= 1.086 \int \pi a^2 Q_V n_d \, ds \\
&= 1.086 \int \pi a^2 Q_V \cdot \frac{n_d}{n_{\text{H}_2}} \cdot n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 1.086 \int \pi a^2 Q_V \cdot \frac{\psi m_{\text{H}_2}}{\frac{4}{3}\pi a^3 \rho_s} \cdot n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 1.086 \int \frac{3Q_V \psi m_{\text{H}_2}}{4a\rho_s} \cdot n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 1.086 \cdot \frac{3Q_V \psi m_{\text{H}_2}}{4a\rho_s} \int n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 1.086 \cdot \frac{3(1.5)(0.005)(3.3474 \times 10^{-24} \text{ g})}{4(0.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm})(2.25 \text{ g cm}^{-3})} \int n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 9.0659 \times 10^{-22} \text{ cm}^2 \int n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= 9.0659 \times 10^{-22} \text{ cm}^2 \cdot N_{\text{H}_2}
\end{aligned}$$

The column density of molecular hydrogen gas, N_{H_2} , is the number gas density, $n_{\text{H}_2}(r)$ integrated along the line of sight in the radial direction from the star. The gas density is related to the mass-loss rate from the star, \dot{M} , and the expansion velocity of the envelope, V_{exp} , as follows $n_{\text{H}_2}(r) = \dot{M}/4\pi r^2 V_{\text{exp}}$. We adopt the mass-loss rate model given by Castro-Carrizo et al. (2007), in which $\dot{M} = 3 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ for $2.5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm} < r < 12.4 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}$ and $\dot{M} = 1.2 \times 10^{-4} M_{\odot}/\text{year}$ for $22.0 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm} < r < 52.0 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}$. We adopt an expansion velocity of $V_{\text{exp}} = 38.0 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ (Dinh-V-Trung et al., 2009). The unit conversion factor to cgs unit is 1.4985×10^{43} .

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{\text{H}_2} &= \int n_{\text{H}_2} \, ds \\
&= \int_{2.5 \times 10^{16}}^{12.4 \times 10^{16}} \frac{(3.0 \times 10^{-4})(1.4985 \times 10^{43})}{38 \cdot s^2} \, ds \\
&\quad + \int_{22.0 \times 10^{16}}^{52.0 \times 10^{16}} \frac{(1.2 \times 10^{-4})(1.4985 \times 10^{43})}{38 \cdot s^2} \, ds \\
&= 1.1831 \times 10^{22} \left(\frac{1}{2.5} - \frac{1}{12.4} \right) \\
&\quad + 4.7323 \times 10^{21} \left(\frac{1}{22.0} - \frac{1}{52.0} \right) \\
&= 3.9023 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$A_V = 9.0659 \times 10^{-22} \text{ cm}^2 \cdot 3.9023 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2} = 3.54$$

Appendix B

Wind Opacity of IRC+10420

Conservation of momentum suggests $\dot{M}v_\infty \simeq \tau(L_*/c)$ (e.g. Kochanek, 2011). \dot{M} is the mass loss rate, v_∞ is terminal outflow velocity, τ is the wind opacity (ignoring dust) and L_* is the stellar luminosity.

Here we assume that all momentum from stellar photons is transferred to the momentum of the gas (but not dust) in the stellar wind and accelerate the wind to terminal velocity. We adopt the following values for the wind parameters, which would lead to a lower bound for the wind opacity, τ .

$$\dot{M} = 3 \times 10^{-4} M_\odot/\text{year}$$

$$v_\infty = 35 \text{ km s}^{-1}$$

$$L_* = 5.4 \times 10^5 L_\odot$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau &= \frac{\dot{M}v_{\infty}c}{L_*} \\
&= \left(\frac{\dot{M}}{M_{\odot}/\text{year}} \right) \cdot (1.9891 \times 10^{33} / 3.15569 \times 10^7) \\
&\quad \times \left(\frac{v_{\infty}}{\text{km s}^{-1}} \right) \cdot 10^5 \times (3 \times 10^{10}) \times \left(\frac{L_*}{10^6 L_{\odot}} \right)^{-1} \cdot (3.839 \times 10^{39})^{-1} \\
&= 49.257 \left(\frac{\dot{M}}{M_{\odot}/\text{year}} \right) \left(\frac{v_{\infty}}{\text{km s}^{-1}} \right) \left(\frac{L_*}{10^6 L_{\odot}} \right)^{-1} \\
&= \frac{49.257(0.0003)(35)}{0.54} = 0.96 \approx 1
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix C

From Doppler Measurement to Spatial Distribution

As we will show in this Appendix that an assumed function of Doppler velocity with respect to the position along the slit, $V_{\text{Dopp}}(x)$, can be uniquely translated to the spatial distribution of the knots in terms of slit position, x , and position along the line of sight, z .

The definitions of the parameters are as follows.

Measured Doppler velocity of the knots, V_{Dopp} , from Humphreys et al. (2002)

Systemic velocity of IRC+10420, V_0

Envelope expansion velocity, V_{exp}

Radial velocity of the knots along the line of sight, V_z

Transverse velocity of the knots perpendicular to the line of sight, V_x

Position along the slit, x

Position along the line of sight, z

Since the Doppler velocity composed of (1) the systemic velocity of the star and the entire envelope, V_0 , (2) the radial expansion velocity of the knots away from the central star, V_{exp} , because the Doppler shift adds up when the

starlight is reflected by the dust in the knots, and (3) the radial component of the expansion velocity, V_z , we have

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{Dopp}} &= V_0 + V_{\text{exp}} + V_z \\ V_z &= (V_{\text{Dopp}} - V_0) - V_{\text{exp}} \end{aligned}$$

Assuming that the envelope expansion velocity V_{exp} is purely along the radial direction, we then have

$$\begin{aligned} V_x^2 + V_z^2 &= V_{\text{exp}}^2 \\ V_x &= \pm \sqrt{V_{\text{exp}}^2 - V_z^2} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} V_x/V_z &= x/z \\ z &= \frac{V_z}{V_x} x \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above relations, we have

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \frac{V_z}{\pm \sqrt{V_{\text{exp}}^2 - V_z^2}} \cdot x \\ &= \frac{(V_{\text{Dopp}}(x) - V_0) - V_{\text{exp}}}{\pm \sqrt{V_{\text{exp}}^2 - [(V_{\text{Dopp}}(x) - V_0) - V_{\text{exp}}]^2}} \cdot x \\ &= \frac{(V_{\text{Dopp}}(x) - V_0) - V_{\text{exp}}}{\pm \sqrt{2(V_{\text{Dopp}}(x) - V_0)V_{\text{exp}} - (V_{\text{Dopp}}(x) - V_0)^2}} \cdot x \end{aligned}$$

Thus this translates uniquely the measured Doppler velocity as a function of slit positions, $V_{\text{Dopp}}(x)$, with spatial distribution of the knots, $z(x)$.

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